

Aging as Meta-Disease: A Comprehensive Framework Integrating Set Theory with Cellular Senescence as Causal Nexus

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Abstract

Whether aging should be classified as a disease remains contentious. We propose a conceptual synthesis: aging is a **meta-disease** - a universal, upstream pathological condition that gives rise to the full spectrum of age-related disorders, as well as the structural and cosmetic changes historically dismissed as “normal aging.” This framework reflects a **Hegelian dialectic**, in which the traditional thesis (aging is a natural process) and the antithesis (aging is a disease) are integrated into a higher-order synthesis. This synthesis preserves the valid insights of each while overcoming their limitations: aging is not a discrete disease, yet it is mechanistically central to disease emergence. It is thus the **generative causal architecture** from which age-related diseases arise - not itself a subset within pathology, but the ontological ground that gives rise to it. This reconceptualization rests on two core pillars. First, a **set-theoretic nosology**: aging defines the universal set **A**. Each age-related disease family constitutes a proper subset within **A** (e.g. cardiovascular disease $V \subset A$, neurodegeneration $N \subset A$). Cosmetic (**K**) and structural (**T**) changes comprise partially overlapping subsets ($K, T \subset A, K \cap T \neq \emptyset$). This formalism enables a precise explanation of comorbidity, multimorbidity, and the structural and cosmetic overlap of age-related conditions. Second, **cellular senescence is the causal nexus**: diverse molecular lesions converge on senescence, defined by irreversible proliferative arrest and activation of the senescence-associated secretory phenotype, and characterized by a distinctive multi-omic signature we term the **senescome**. Senescence functions as a pivotal biological switch - an “**event horizon**” - beyond which transient molecular insults are converted into chronic, system-wide dysfunction. Through these mechanisms, senescence is the **causal generating set (S)** inside **A** that initiates and propagates the various disease subsets. Cancer (**C**) is the exceptional set that reflects escape from senescence and lies largely outside **S**. This meta-disease framework situates **geroscience** within a causal ontology, defining aging as the generative source of pathology. As the antecedent ground of disease, aging thus emerges as the logical primary therapeutic target. Integrating these concepts clarifies terminology and provides formal coherence to International Classification of Diseases extension code XT9T (“*Ageing-related*”) and stem code MG2A (“*Ageing associated decline in intrinsic capacity*”). It also provides practical levers for advancing biomarker portfolios, composite clinical trial endpoints, mechanism-based therapeutic development, regulatory frameworks, and reimbursement models for geroprotective interventions. We conclude by proposing a policy roadmap for translating the meta-disease paradigm into coordinated clinical, regulatory, and public health action, and by examining its implications for the purpose and future of medicine.

Keywords: aging, meta-disease, Hegelian dialectic, set theory, cellular senescence, causal nexus, event horizon, International Classification of Diseases, ICD-11, geroscience, longevity dividend

1 Introduction

A longstanding debate in biogerontology centers on whether aging should be classified as a disease. Two well-defined perspectives have emerged. One side argues that aging is **not** a disease, emphasizing its universality, its status as a natural part of the life cycle, and the conceptual, regulatory, and ethical challenges associated with treating it as a pathological condition (Rattan 2014; Powell and Chen 2017; Fulop et al. 2019; Mendoza-Núñez and Mendoza-Soto 2024; Al-Juhany 2025). The other side believes aging **is** a disease, citing growing evidence that it is a progressive, degenerative process with identifiable mechanisms that are increasingly amenable to intervention (Caplan 2015; De Winter 2015; Bulterijs et al. 2015; Zhavoronkov and Bhullar 2015; Marín Penella 2024). Other insightful and nuanced, although somewhat inconclusive, analyses have also been made (Izaks and Westendorp 2003; Gladyshev and Gladyshev 2016; Saborido and García-Barranquero 2022).

At its core, the persistence of this debate reflects not a deficit of empirical data, but a deeper conceptual uncertainty regarding **how biological science distinguishes natural processes associated with the life cycle from pathological states**.

This conceptual divide has profoundly shaped how aging is treated in medicine and biomedical research. When aging is regarded as a natural background process, medical systems tend to separate age-related conditions such as cancer, heart disease, neurodegeneration, osteoporosis, and so on, into distinct categories (Niccoli and Partridge 2012; Kennedy et al. 2014). Aging itself becomes, in a sense, *ignored*: not something to be directly measured, regulated, and treated. As a result, funding and clinical strategies primarily focus on **downstream** diseases rather than the upstream processes that drive them. This paradigm is reinforced by the absence of formal regulatory pathways for aging as a treatable condition. As highlighted by Stambler (Stambler 2017), historical, conceptual, and policy barriers have systematically prevented aging from being addressed as a medical indication. Consequently, research remains fragmented, investment limited, and progress in developing therapies that directly target aging has been comparatively slow (Bulterijs et al. 2015; Zhavoronkov and Bhullar 2015).

Conversely, labeling aging as a disease introduces its own set of problems. While it underscores its biological seriousness, it also oversimplifies a complex, system-level process. Aging is **not merely one disease among many**, and viewing it as such fails to capture its true role. Both sides of the debate are grounded in valid insights: one emphasizes aging's universality and complexity; the other its pathological consequences and potential tractability. Yet neither framework, in isolation, provides a complete picture.

Part of the semantic tension arises from the fact that aging is evolutionarily “natural” - a complex trait shaped by trade-offs - (Hamilton 1966; Kirkwood 1977) while simultaneously being

medically destructive. This dual status helps explain the persistence of the debate: evolutionary explanations and clinical normativity address fundamentally different questions.

Moving forward will require a new approach - one that reconciles the truth in both positions and provides a clearer understanding of the fundamental nature of aging.

To this end, we framed the problem through the logic of the **Hegelian dialectic**, wherein progress in understanding occurs through the reconciliation of oppositional views into a higher-order synthesis (Hegel 1807). In this triadic structure, a dominant position (thesis) gives rise to its contradiction (antithesis), and their tension is resolved in a **sublation** (*Aufhebung*): a new conceptual unity that both negates and preserves the truth of each prior stance (Hegel 1812).

Applied to the aging-as-disease debate, this dialectical framework yields the following:

Thesis: Aging is a natural process - intrinsic to life, and fundamentally distinct from disease, which is a deviation from normal function.

Antithesis: Aging is a disease, as defined by its underlying mechanisms, many of which overlap with recognized pathologies.

Under scrutiny, each position is partially valid but logically insufficient. The semantic incongruity stems from conflating *process* and *condition*, resulting in a category error (Ryle 1949). Aging is not simply a disease, as it is universal, continuous, and **causally upstream** of specific pathological states; yet neither can it be dismissed as benign, given its role in generating nearly all major causes of morbidity and mortality. To resolve this semantic impasse, we must sublimate thesis and antithesis into a higher understanding.

Synthesis: Aging is a **meta-disease** - not a singular disease entity, but a **causal, systemic, and higher-order process** that gives rise to multiple diseases as downstream effects (Figure 1).

The prefix *meta-* (from the Greek μετά, meaning “beyond” or “at a higher level”) denotes an organizing or generative relationship, something that governs or structures a set of related entities rather than belonging to it (Bateson 1972; Oxford English Dictionary). By this logic, a **meta-disease** is not one disease among others but the **causal framework** from which multiple diseases arise. Aging fulfills this role precisely. It operates at a higher ontological level than discrete pathologies, representing a systemic and continuous process that shapes the probability, co-occurrence, and progression of virtually all age-related conditions.

Specific diseases can be understood as *first-order* failures within biological subsystems, whereas aging is a *second-order* or **meta-level deformation** of the organism’s regulatory architecture that

gives rise to those failures. This formulation preserves the conceptual distinction between cause and effect, avoiding the category error (Ryle 1949) of labeling aging as a single disease while capturing its mechanistic centrality. Importantly, it also corrects the inadequacies of alternative descriptors: terms like “**risk factor**” or “**syndrome**” imply either weak association or descriptive clustering without sufficient causal depth.

Rather than treating age-related diseases as isolated failures, *meta-disease* aligns with network medicine, which shows that many pathologies emerge from system-level perturbations rather than single lesions (Barabási et al. 2011). Viewed through this lens, aging can be understood as the **generative field of dysfunction**, within which age-related diseases are local attractors (Huang 2009). In Hegelian terms, this reframing constitutes a true **sublation** (*Aufhebung* - *integrating and uplifting both opposing ideas*): it dissolves the binary opposition between “natural process” and “pathology,” retains the essential insights of each position, and elevates them into a more comprehensive ontological framework (Figure 1).

Figure 1: *Hegelian synthesis of the aging-disease paradigm.* This schematic presents the Hegelian dialectic applied to whether aging is “natural” or a “disease.” A thesis (aging is a natural, universal process distinct from disease) and an antithesis (aging is a disease, given its pathological mechanisms) are visualized merging into a higher-order synthesis: **aging is a meta-disease**. We show aging positioned at a meta-level, an upstream pathological state that generates multiple downstream diseases, thereby preserving truths from both viewpoints. By explicitly naming aging a meta-disease, we define a linguistic shift (Sapir-Whorf influence) that reframes aging as a treatable condition,

supporting the argument that this conceptual change can clarify thinking and galvanize new research and policy approaches.

Having conceptually reframed aging, we next consider how the words we use (and the ICD-11 taxonomy) shape scientific perspective. It is important to realize that language is not just a passive correlate of biomedical reality. The principle of linguistic relativity, as articulated in the Sapir-Whorf hypothesis, posits that the structure of language significantly influences cognition and perception (Whorf 1956; Lucy 1997). Applied in this context, explicitly *defining* aging as a meta-disease will reshape both scientific and societal perceptions of aging. It allows us to move beyond symptom-based classification toward a **process-based understanding of systemic breakdown**, positioning aging as the pathological ground from which age-related diseases emerge. **Because language shapes thought**, precise terminology facilitates conceptual clarity, encourages focused research, and motivates effective intervention strategies. Framing aging through this explicit linguistic lens thus fosters a more coherent and proactive approach to age-related health challenges.

Beyond semantics, aging's relationship with its associated conditions can be formally articulated by set theory. This formalization draws on classical set theory (Halmos 1960) and aligns with contemporary models of multimorbidity in which overlapping disease clusters are increasingly represented as intersecting sets rather than discrete entities (Prados-Torres et al. 2014). Within this framework, aging itself represents the universal set, **A**, encompassing distinct yet interconnected subsets such as cardiovascular disease (**V**), neurodegenerative disorders (**N**), and so forth. This mathematical representation makes explicit the overlapping and interconnected nature of aging-related pathologies, providing a precise yet intuitive language for clinical research and health policy development.

Furthermore, our meta-disease framework crucially identifies cellular senescence not simply as one of many hallmarks of aging, but rather as the critical **causal nexus** (a central point where multiple causes converge and one or more effects emerge) linking molecular damage to overt clinical manifestations (Bhatia-Dey et al. 2016). Senescence acts as a pivotal biological switch, an **“event horizon”** converting diverse molecular insults such as telomere attrition, genomic instability, oxidative stress, or epigenetic drift, into systemic physiological deterioration via tissue and organ breakdown and the senescence-associated secretory phenotype (SASP), characterized by age-accumulating proteolytic and signaling activity that disrupts extracellular matrix homeostasis and proliferative control (West et al. 1989, 1996). Through these mechanisms, **senescence gives rise to a causal generating set (S)** within the universal set of aging (**A**), within which it **initiates and propagates the subsets that comprise the various age-related disease subsets**.

This causal nexus architecture provides a formal philosophical foundation for the **geroscience hypothesis**, the idea that targeting the mechanisms of aging directly can delay or prevent multiple

diseases simultaneously (Kennedy et al. 2014). Rather than addressing each age-related condition in isolation, geroscience seeks to intervene in the upstream biology that underlies them all. Formalizing aging as a meta-disease **gives structural coherence to this hypothesis**: it explains why a single intervention can yield benefits across multiple pathological domains, and it justifies treating aging as a primary therapeutic target rather than a mere background condition.

Importantly, conceptualizing aging as a meta-disease has profound practical implications. Clinically, it enables the use of composite trial endpoints (such as **time to first morbidity across multiple age-related diseases**), significantly improving trial design and efficiency (Rolland et al. 2023). From a regulatory standpoint, it aligns naturally with recent International Classification of Diseases (ICD) coding advancements, including extension codes like XT9T (“*Ageing-related*”) and MG2A (“*Ageing associated decline in intrinsic capacity*”), and provides a clearer rationale for regulatory pathways explicitly focused on geroprotective interventions (Justice et al. 2016; Kritchevsky et al. 2025).

Economically, recognizing aging as a meta-disease allows health economists to quantify and communicate the substantial “**longevity dividend**” achievable by interventions targeting aging’s underlying mechanisms, particularly cellular senescence (Olshansky et al. 2007; Scott et al. 2021). Such interventions promise significant cost-offset potential by simultaneously delaying or reducing the incidence of multiple chronic conditions (Goldman et al. 2013).

From an ethical and societal perspective, defining aging as a meta-disease reframes late-life decline as modifiable rather than inevitable, thereby encouraging engagement in preventive health behaviors and reinforcing the moral imperative to reduce avoidable suffering (Binstock et al. 2006; De Grey and Rae 2007). Framing aging as treatable, not only shifts scientific investment but alters public expectations, catalyzing cultural realignment toward health preservation rather than passive acceptance of decline. Importantly, designating aging as a meta-disease is not meant to label or stigmatize older individuals as “sick,” but rather to incorporate the reality that the underlying processes are amenable to intervention. In other words, we can use “meta-disease” as a regulatory operational category (like hypertension or hyperlipidemia): upstream, measurable, and treatable; rather than a value judgment about individuals.

In sum, defining aging as a meta-disease is not merely a semantic exercise but a necessary step toward **unifying and accelerating geroscience research**, clarifying clinical and regulatory strategies, optimizing health economics, and enhancing public health communication. This conceptual shift lays a coherent foundation for addressing one of humanity’s greatest medical challenges: transforming aging from an inevitable decline into a manageable, preventable condition.

We continue by formalizing the meta-disease concept in nosological and set-theoretic terms in Section 2, before turning to mechanism, translation, and implications in Sections 3 through 6.

2 Nosological Foundations of Aging as Meta-Disease

Nosology is the branch of medical science dedicated to the classification and categorization of diseases (Boorse 1977; Reznek 1987). A robust nosological framework ensures clarity in disease definition, improves diagnostic precision, facilitates effective communication among healthcare professionals, and supports coherent regulatory and reimbursement processes. Historically, aging has lacked formal nosological classification, thereby hampering coordinated progress across research, clinical practice, and health policy domains (Zhavoronkov and Bhullar 2015; Stambler 2017; Khaltourina et al. 2020).

2.1 International Classification of Diseases-11 Precedent

The ICD, developed by the World Health Organization (WHO), provides the global standard for disease classification, ensuring consistency in clinical diagnosis and epidemiological surveillance, and health system reporting. The recent ICD-11 revision marks a pivotal shift toward explicit acknowledgment of aging, introducing the aforementioned extension codes XT9T and stem codes like MG2A, the latter rooted in geriatric functional frameworks such as intrinsic capacity (Cesari et al. 2018).

These inclusions represent an important nosological precedent, by recognizing aging as a shared etiological substrate across disease manifestations (Franceschi et al. 2018). However, while the codes acknowledge aging as a modifier, they stop short of classifying it as a pathological entity in its own right. Accordingly, some of us have advocated for full recognition of aging within ICD nosology (Stambler 2017), arguing that a higher-order classification would more accurately align biological causality with clinical and regulatory structures.

This is precisely where the concept of aging as a meta-disease offers a coherent and actionable solution: it provides the missing conceptual level that makes these codes more coherent and usable. We propose the **formal recognition of aging** as the universal, upstream pathological process that both drives and encompasses age-related diseases, a position increasingly endorsed within the geroscience and longevity policy communities as essential for aligning biological causality with clinical and regulatory frameworks (Zhavoronkov and Bhullar 2015). Such recognition would not only clarify the biological and clinical meaning of the ICD-11 codes, it would also **complete their conceptual trajectory**. Reclassifying aging in this manner would solidify its role across medical domains: it would enable more integrated clinical management, justify the use of composite endpoints in trials that span multiple disease categories, and guide the targeted development of upstream therapeutics. Furthermore, it would streamline regulatory approval for geroprotective interventions, provide a legitimate framework for reimbursement of treatments that target fundamental aging processes, and support more effective public health strategies focused on prevention and resilience rather than late-stage disease control.

In summary, while the innovations introduced by ICD-11 establish an important foundation, full nosological recognition of aging as a higher-than-disease-level entity; namely, a **meta-disease** is required to optimally advance geriatrics and gerontology. To operationalize this nosological claim, we now formalize aging in set-theoretic terms.

2.2 A Set-Theoretic Model of Aging as Meta-Disease

To rigorously define aging as a meta-disease, we propose a set-theoretic approach. Set theory offers a precise and consistent formalism for representing the hierarchical relationships between aging and its associated pathologies, ensuring both conceptual precision and practical utility. This mathematical formalism aligns with ontological methodologies in biomedical informatics, which emphasize that disease classifications should be modeled as structured hierarchies reflecting causal and conceptual containment (Smith and Ceusters 2010; Schulz and Jansen 2013).

The data comprising each set will necessarily be multi-omic in nature. Multi-omic frameworks integrate heterogeneous cellular and molecular layers including cellular developmental, anatomical, and evolutionary hierarchies, genomic, epigenomic, transcriptomic, proteomic, and metabolomic data, to reconstruct system-level causal architectures (Hasin et al. 2017; Subramanian et al. 2020). Applied to aging, these integrative approaches reveal convergent molecular signatures across tissues and species (Zhang et al. 2022), laying the groundwork for a comprehensive set-theoretic representation. This motivates a state-space view of aging in which tissue-level ‘damage-and-response’ measurements define the coordinates from which age-associated outcomes arise.

Accordingly, we formally define aging itself as the universal set (A), i.e., the universal aging-associated pathological state-space.

Elements of A are biological state vectors indexed by individual and timepoint, with tissue/organ “damage-and-response” measurements as coordinates; disease subsets are regions of that state-space. In practice, set membership is inferred probabilistically, via multi-marker signatures and latent-variable estimates, so the formal relations express causal/structural organization rather than strict binary classification.

Within A , we define a **special subset, S** , corresponding to cellular senescence, as a **causal generating subset within A ($S \subset A$)**. Unlike organ- or diagnosis-defined subsets (V , N , etc.), **S is defined by causal mediation**: it represents the senescence-mediated region of aging pathology, through which diverse upstream molecular insults are **integrated** and from which broad downstream dysfunction is **propagated** (via permanent arrest and SASP-driven signaling). Membership in S can be defined using specific senescence-associated multi-omic and functional signatures. We propose the term “**senescome**” to represent the totality of molecular signatures associated with cellular senescence. Multi-omic characterization of senescent cells across tissues is advancing rapidly (Song et al. 2020; Li et al. 2025), and large-scale efforts such as the SenNet

Consortium are actively building molecular atlases of senescence, moving the field toward a robust operationalization of said senescome.

Structurally, the senescome would comprise multiple layers: a **core signature** shared across senescence types (e.g., p16^{INK4a}, p21^{CIP1}, SA- β -gal activity), **tissue-specific modules** reflecting local SASP composition and microenvironmental interactions, and **trigger-specific variants** distinguishing replicative senescence from oncogene-induced, DNA-damage-induced, or therapy-induced forms (Prasanna et al. 2021). A complete **senescome atlas**, analogous to the transcriptome or proteome, would enable precise **stratification of patients by senescence burden and type**, guide tissue-targeted intervention, and provide the molecular vocabulary for defining membership in **S**. Defining and mapping the senescome thus represents a *key near-term objective* for operationalizing the meta-disease framework.

Within **S** itself, distinct yet overlapping subsets represent individual categories of age-related conditions. Illustrative subsets include cardiovascular diseases (**V**), neurodegenerative disorders (**N**), immunosenescence (**I**), dermatological conditions (**D**), musculoskeletal disorders (**M**), and cosmetic (**K**) or structural changes (**T**). In this model, what we identify as a “cardiovascular disease” (**V**) or a “neurodegenerative disease” (**N**) corresponds to the condition where the senescence-mediated regime **S** has established itself in the cardiovascular system or the nervous system, respectively. Accordingly, these phenotype subsets remain minimal or unpopulated **until** senescent cells accumulate in the specific tissue: molecular damage **alone** in a tissue (an element of **A** *outside* of **S**) is insufficient to produce the full disease phenotype. Put another way, membership in a disease subset (**V**, **N**, etc.) requires prior membership in **S**; damage without senescence - (**A** \setminus **S**) - is necessary but **not sufficient** for age-related pathology. The characteristic age-related disease in a given organ only **truly** emerges once **S** expands into that tissue. Thus, each disease-family subset can be understood as a tissue-specific subregion of **S** within **A**: a zone of the state-space where senescent-cell burden drives dysfunction in that organ system.

These subsets are not mutually exclusive; indeed, **intersections among them represent comorbid or multimorbid conditions** commonly observed in old age (Prados-Torres et al. 2014). In essence, **S** is being distributed across multiple anatomical compartments - i.e., there are senescence-driven pathological states in more than one tissue at the same time. For example, venous stasis dermatitis resides at the intersection of dermatological and vascular subsets (**D** \cap **V**), while vascular dementia represents an intersection of cardiovascular and neurodegenerative subsets (**V** \cap **N**). Such intersections demonstrate the interconnected nature of aging-related diseases, highlighting the importance of treating aging as a unified pathological process - a meta-disease - rather than isolated phenomena.

This set-theoretic framing lets us define multimorbidity patterns as **Venn-diagram-like regions** generated from the disease-domain subsets (**{V, N, D,...}**) within the senescence-mediated regime (**S**) - i.e., regions obtained by unions and intersections, as well as set

differences among these domains (e.g., $(V \setminus N)$ and $(N \setminus V)$). This provides a systematic framework for characterizing comorbidity and multimorbidity (Valderas et al. 2009; Ng et al. 2018; Alvarez-Galvez and Vegas-Lozano 2022) and supports clearer diagnostic stratification and more precise clinical trial design, including prespecified multimorbidity strata and multi-domain composite endpoints (Justice et al. 2016; Cummings and Kritchevsky 2022; Rolland et al. 2023; Kritchevsky et al. 2025).

It is important to note that not **all** age-related pathology follows the senescence-mediated route. **Cancer (C), in particular**, represents a special case: by definition, malignant cells achieve uncontrolled growth by bypassing or escaping the senescence checkpoint, essentially circumventing the **S** regime that would normally halt damaged cells. In set-theoretic terms, cancer occupies its own subset ($C \subset A$) that is largely disjoint from **S** (formally, $S \cap C \approx \emptyset$). We say “*largely*” because even though cancer is defined by senescence checkpoint evasion, in *some* cases senescence may still be present in the tumor microenvironment or induced by therapy; thus, **C** is not well-modeled as a subset of **S**. Even though cancer still arises from the same universal state-space **A** (accumulated molecular damage), it typically does so via a trajectory that **evades** senescence, unlike the other chronic pathologies of aging that accumulate within **S**. We explore the mechanistic basis and empirical evidence for this distinction more in Section 3; for now, the key point is that **S** and **C** represent two divergent pathways through the landscape of **A** - one (**S**) funneling damage into chronic degenerative diseases, and the other (**C**) leading to malignant transformation by avoiding the senescence barrier.

In summary, **aging-as-meta-disease** can be formally understood as a hierarchy of sets: **A** is the all-encompassing set of aging-related pathological states, within which **S** is the emergent senescence-driven subspace that causally underpins most age-related diseases. The familiar clinical disease categories correspond to **subsets of S (within A)** tied to specific tissues, becoming populated **only** when cells in those tissues become senescent. Overlaps among these subsets capture the phenomenon of multimorbidity, and the outlier status of cancer (**C**) highlights senescence’s role as a selective causal filter. This architecture yields a central **falsifiable prediction**: interventions that contract **S** should **yield correlated reductions across multiple disease subsets, and the breadth of benefit should scale with the magnitude and distribution of S reduction**. Next, we will build upon this by introducing several conceptual and visual frameworks that illustrate how aging operates as a meta-disease and how senescence **orchestrates the transition** from molecular damage to overt pathology.

2.3 Conceptual Frameworks for Understanding Aging as a Meta-Disease

Conceptualizing aging as a meta-disease enables systematic interpretation of the complex interactions among molecular damage, cellular senescence, and age-related diseases through various structured frameworks, employing comprehensive and integrated multi-omic data. Four useful conceptual models for capturing these relationships are causal set mapping, conceptual

layering, causal containment diagrams, and set-theoretic models. Each provides a unique lens for examining the interconnectedness and hierarchical structure underlying aging (Figure 2).

1. **Causal Set Mapping** (Temporal and Directional) (Figure 2a): In this directed network diagram, arrows trace the causal flow from initial molecular damage to end-stage diseases; nodes represent distinct events or biological states, whereas edges denote directional causation. Upstream damage (DNA mutations, telomere erosion, epigenetic drift, etc.) causes meta-disease (**A**) which leads into cellular senescence (**S**), a pivotal node. From senescent cells, further arrows radiate to various age-related diseases (e.g., cardiovascular disease (**V**), neurodegeneration (**N**) and cosmetic changes (**K**)). Notably, cancer (**C**) is a *special case*: it *either* branches directly from molecular damage, bypassing the senescence node entirely, *or escapes* from senescence. This shows that while most age-related pathologies are downstream of senescence, cancers emerge via a separate route.
2. **Conceptual Layering** (Hierarchical Abstraction) (Figure 2b): This model emphasizes hierarchical emergence, organizing aging into conceptual levels: starting from physical insults (radiation, toxins, infections etc.), leading to molecular damage (telomere attrition, epigenetic noise), followed by cellular senescence as the pivotal causal nexus. Senescence then drives pathophysiological states like inflammaging and impairment of cell proliferation, finally resulting in clinical phenotypes such as cardiovascular disease, diabetes, and neurodegeneration. This layered perspective clarifies dependencies and emergent properties at each biological level.
3. **Causal Containment Diagram** (Spatial & Visual) (Figure 2c): In this diagram, nested and overlapping circles are used as a **conceptual causal-domain visualization**, *not* as a strict set-inclusion diagram. **Moving inward denotes increasing causal mediation/constraint**: the outermost, largest set represents meta-disease (**A**), encompassing the full state-space of upstream molecular damage. Nested within is cellular senescence (**S**), indicating its role as the mediating causal nexus bridging molecular damage to disease manifestations. Downstream diseases such as neurodegeneration (**N**), cardiovascular disease (**V**), and dermal changes (**D**) are represented as subsets within **S**, highlighting shared pathological mechanisms. Overlaps, such as vascular dementia ($V \cap N$) and venous stasis dermatitis ($D \cap V$) indicate comorbid conditions. Cancer is uniquely positioned within the broader meta-disease set but largely **outside** the senescence one, visually reinforcing its distinct causal trajectory that often bypasses senescence checkpoint mechanisms. *The formal set-theoretic relationships are specified separately in the following set-theoretic model.*
4. **Set-Theoretic Model** (Formal & Logical) (Figure 2d): This formal framework clearly defines relationships through mathematical set theory. The meta-disease represents the universal set (**A**), encompassing all outcomes from molecular damage. Within this, a subset (**S**) contains diseases mediated by cellular senescence. Another subset (**C**) includes cancer, specifically defined by its capacity to circumvent senescence checkpoints. Formally, this model clarifies that while subsets **S** and **C** are both part of the universal set **A**, they remain

largely *distinct* ($S \cap C \approx \emptyset$), providing clarity on the role of senescence as a selective causal filter.

Together, these four frameworks - causal set mapping, conceptual layering, causal containment diagrams, and set-theoretic modeling - provide a multidimensional understanding of aging. Each contributes distinct analytic strengths, including temporal flow, hierarchical emergence, spatial relationships, and logical rigor, to the conceptualization of age-related pathology. They all show aging's processes as upstream of and encompassing specific diseases. In practice, set membership can be quantified using multi-omic data, such as pathway-activation drift (Aliper et al. 2015; Makarev et al. 2017) and many other **senescome-derived features** (as defined above).

In summary, integrating strong nosological foundations with a rigorous set-theoretic model provides a comprehensive and actionable framework for defining aging as a meta-disease, as well as a logical relationship for the diverse anatomical, histological, and cellular “-omic” data necessary for the development of future advanced relational databases of aging. This conceptual approach will also facilitate enhanced scientific collaboration, improved clinical trial designs, coherent regulatory strategies, economically robust health planning, and clearer public health communication, fundamentally reshaping our collective approach to aging and age-related diseases.

Figure 2: 2a. Causal set mapping of aging's pathway. In this directed network diagram, arrows trace the causal flow from initial molecular damage to end-stage diseases; nodes represent distinct events or biological states, whereas edges denote directional causation (green edge = cause; red edge = effect). Upstream damage (DNA mutations, telomere erosion, epigenetic drift, etc.) causes meta-disease (**A**) which leads into **cellular senescence (S)**, a pivotal node. From senescent cells, further arrows radiate to various age-related diseases (e.g., cardiovascular disease (**V**), neurodegeneration (**N**) and cosmetic changes (**K**)). Notably, **cancer (C)** is a special case: it either branches directly from molecular damage, bypassing the senescence node entirely, *or* escapes from senescence (dotted arrow). This highlights that while most age-related pathologies are downstream of senescence, cancers emerge via a separate route. The figure illustrates the meta-disease concept by emphasizing senescence as the key transition point between widespread damage and the multitude of age-associated diseases, while explaining cancer's exceptional trajectory.

2b. Hierarchical layering of aging processes. This figure depicts aging as a stack of conceptual layers, each emerging from the one below. As before, a green edge denotes cause, whereas red is effect. At the base, **physical stressors** (e.g., radiation, infections, toxins) give rise to the next layer of **molecular damage** (genomic instability, telomere attrition, misfolded proteins, etc.), which causes meta-disease, **A**. Above that, a layer represents **cellular senescence, S**, the causal nexus where accumulated damage triggers permanent cell-cycle arrest and the pro-inflammatory SASP. Building on senescence is a layer of **pathophysiological changes** (such as inflammation, stem cell exhaustion) that spread systemically. At the top layer, these changes manifest **clinical aging phenotypes**: the familiar **age-related diseases** and frailties (cardiovascular (**V**), neurodegenerative (**N**), etc.). By showing how each higher level arises from the lower levels, we reinforce that senescence is the pivotal bridge linking microscopic damage to the macroscopic diseases of aging, thereby underpinning the meta-disease framework.

2c. Causal containment diagram (conceptual): Nested and overlapping regions depict **causal mediation layers** (outer \rightarrow inner), **not** strict set inclusion among a single class of elements. The outer region **A** represents aging as a meta-disease: a broad upstream domain of molecular damage and organism-level dysregulation from which late-life pathologies emerge. Nested within **A**, region **S** denotes the **senescence-mediated regime**, highlighting cellular senescence as a key mediator that converts diverse upstream

insults into propagating dysfunction. Downstream disease domains (e.g., cardiovascular **V**, neurodegenerative **N**, dermal **D**) are shown largely within **S**, and overlaps indicate shared mechanisms and mixed phenotypes/comorbidity (e.g., vascular dementia at the $V \cap N$ overlap, venous stasis dermatitis at the $D \cap V$ overlap). **Cancer (C)** is depicted within **A** but largely outside **S**, reflecting malignancy's defining route of **senescence-checkpoint bypass/escape**. Formal set-theoretic relationships among **A**, **S**, and disease subsets are specified in the following panel 2d. **2d. Set-theoretic model**. This diagram uses formal set notation to define relationships between aging, senescence, and disease. **Set A** (the universal set) encompasses all age-related phenotypes, effectively aging's entire pathological state-space. Within **A**, **Set S** is shown to include outcomes causally mediated by senescence (most chronic diseases and infirmities of aging). Separately, **Set C** represents cancer outcomes. We explicitly indicate that **S** and **C** are largely disjoint ($S \cap C \approx \emptyset$): senescence-driven conditions and cancers share the same root origin in aging (both subsets of **A**) but have minimal overlap because cancer cells escape senescence. The model describes the meta-disease concept by showing that treating aging means chiefly targeting **S** (without directly preventing cancer, which follows a different pathway). We provide a logical map of how various disease subsets relate within the "universal set" of aging, highlighting senescence as the defining factor for most age-related diseases.

The nosological and set-theoretic scaffold is only explanatory if it is anchored to a specific mediator that can translate heterogeneous upstream damage into persistent, system-wide dysfunction. In other words, the architecture of aging as a meta-disease requires a mechanistic "**hinge**" that explains why diverse insults yield clustered, overlapping late-life pathologies. We therefore now shift from structure to mechanism by further explicating cellular senescence as the causal nexus.

3 Cellular Senescence: From Hallmark to Causal Nexus

Various molecular and cellular "hallmarks" have been identified as potential contributors to aging, including genomic instability, telomere attrition, epigenetic alterations, etc. (López-Otín et al. 2013, 2023). Of these, **cellular senescence uniquely represents a pivotal causal nexus** connecting upstream molecular damage with downstream physiological dysfunction (Bhatia-Dey et al. 2016) (Figure 3). In philosophical terms, a causal nexus is a **hub** where multiple causes converge and one or more downstream effects emerge (Salmon 1984). Although other hallmarks are in the causal chain, they tend to either *converge* on senescence or *require* senescence to produce system-wide damage, whereas senescence *by itself* causes chronic dysfunction: once a cell has become senescent, it can autonomously foment local inflammation and tissue degeneration. In this way, cellular senescence serves as the **central mechanism** by which diffuse upstream damage is translated into the unified, macroscopic phenotype of organismal aging. In the set-theoretic model described above in Section 2.2, this is the biological transition by which senescence defines and expands the senescence-mediated regime ($S \subset A$) within the universal aging-associated pathological state-space **A**, converting diffuse molecular injury into self-sustaining tissue and organ breakdown, thereby generating the macroscopic manifestations of aging. Senescence is pivotal because it is the *conduit between the microscopic and tissue scales*: it simultaneously destroys regenerative cell supply (through stable arrest) and installs an active remodeling program (through the SASP), which together drives the physical failure of tissue architecture, the most universal signature of aging. Thus, our framework **subsumes and clarifies the hallmarks rather than competes with them**. Within this architecture, genomic instability, telomere attrition, epigenetic alterations, etc. function as **upstream** triggers that push cells toward **S**; mitochondrial

dysfunction and loss of proteostasis act as accelerants; while stem cell exhaustion and altered intercellular communication emerge as downstream **consequences** of S expansion. Senescence is **not** one hallmark among equals but the **nexus through which the others exert their pathological effects**.

At the cellular level, senescence is defined as a stable and essentially irreversible arrest of the cell cycle, enforced by stress-responsive checkpoint pathways (Campisi and d'Adda Di Fagagna 2007). A cell that crosses into senescence permanently loses its ability to proliferate, which over time **erodes the body's regenerative capacity**. Tissues rely on cycles of cell division (from stem cells, progenitors, and functional somatic cells) to repair damage and maintain structure; senescence **depletes this renewal potential**, leading to cumulative architectural distortions and functional decline (Childs et al. 2015; He and Sharpless 2017). Moreover, senescent cells do not sit idle; they actively secrete a potent mix of pro-inflammatory cytokines, proteases, and growth factors - via the SASP, which **transforms the cell's microenvironment**, recruiting immune cells and propagating "bystander" stress in neighboring cells. In acute contexts (for example, wound healing or tumor suppression), a transient senescence response may be beneficial. But when senescent cells persist and accumulate, their incessant SASP signaling **degrades tissue integrity and promotes chronic inflammation**, creating self-perpetuating zones of dysfunction. Over time, the **systemic buildup of senescent cells** across multiple organs coalesces into the familiar manifestations of aging: frailty, organ system failures, and the spectrum of chronic diseases we see in old age. In theoretical terms, senescence fits this causal-nexus role (Salmon 1984; Bhatia-Dey et al. 2016). Put simply, senescence is the **fulcrum of aging's machinery**: a single biological switch that unifies cause and effect by turning molecular damage into organism-level dysfunction.

Figure 3: *Cellular senescence as the causal nexus.* Here we show **senescent cells** at the center of aging’s pathology network. Multiple icons on the left depict diverse **damage inputs**: telomere erosion, cytoplasmic, extracellular matrix (ECM), mitochondrial, and DNA damage, oncogene activation, epigenetic changes, and other lesions all converging on the cell to trigger senescence. This collective, accumulated damage pushes cells over the “event horizon” (dashed red line) into the senescent state in which they cease dividing (shown as red and orange cells) and secrete pro-inflammatory cytokines, proteases, and growth factors (SASP, shown as yellow “bolts”), becoming the causal nexus of aging. We then show this feeding into the development of **age-related diseases** in multiple organs. By visually uniting many upstream causes into one pivotal cell state that then drives multi-organ decline, we reinforce that cellular senescence is the **central mechanism** by which aging damage is transmuted into the broad spectrum of age-associated diseases.

3.1 Senescence as the Event Horizon of Aging

We propose that cellular senescence functions as an “**event horizon**” (Rindler 1956) in the aging process: a critical threshold beyond which damage becomes persistent dysfunction (Figure 4). On the near side of this horizon, damage may be resolved and functional regeneration achieved by the return of the cell to a non-activated state. But once crossed, a cell enters senescence and the change becomes essentially irreversible. The cell is locked in a durable growth-arrested state and begins emitting SASP factors, initiating cascading effects. In effect, crossing this horizon marks the functional tipping point at which a cell’s damage is no longer contained to that cell alone - it is

now broadcast to the surrounding tissue, permanently altering the local environment. In **set-theoretic terms** (Stoddard 1980), this horizon defines the boundary of a **senescence-mediated subregion (S)** within the universal set **A** of aging-related phenotypes. Cells that fail to reach this threshold remain outside **S**; those that do reach and cross it then “populate” the aforementioned disease subsets such as **V, N, K**, and so on. In other words, cellular senescence can be viewed as a biological mechanism that *populates and expands subsets* within the universal set (**A**) of aging-related conditions.

Crucially, when enough cells in a tissue undergo senescence, these individual points of no return **add up** to a *tipping point* for the organism. The spread of SASP-driven signals from senescent cells can induce further dysfunction in neighboring cells (including bystander senescence), creating a **feed-forward loop of deterioration**. Thus, senescence is not only a cell-intrinsic event horizon, but also a **collective threshold for tissues**: as senescent cells accumulate, tissues transition from healthy maintenance into a state of entrenched, self-propagating degeneration. This helps explain why aging manifests as a simultaneous, multi-organ decline. Different organ systems may experience diverse upstream insults, but once their cells cross into senescence, the outcome **converges on the same pattern of chronic inflammation, tissue breakdown, and loss of function**. In this way, cellular senescence establishes an irreversible beachhead of pathology that drives aging at the macroscopic level.

By contrast, **cancer (C)** occupies a special position. Both degenerative diseases and cancers arise from similar age-accumulating molecular insults (DNA mutations, telomere erosion, etc.), but their paths diverge at the senescence checkpoint. In most tissues, cells that incur significant damage are pressed into senescence, leading to degeneration. Cancer cells, by contrast, escape the event horizon - they achieve immortality by disabling the very tumor-suppressor pathways that enforce senescence (Campisi and d’Adda Di Fagagna 2007; Collado and Serrano 2010). **In our formalism, $C \subset A$ but $C \cap S \approx \emptyset$.** Cancer thus represents an **exceptional subset**: still driven by aging’s damage, but defined by *its ability to evade the very mechanism that constrains other age-related diseases*. A precancerous cell that evades senescence will continue dividing unchecked, evolving into a malignancy instead of contributing to degenerative aging. This bifurcation in cell fate (senescence versus unchecked proliferation) offers a mechanistic explanation for how the same upstream aging process yields two starkly different outcomes: degenerative disease when the senescence threshold is obeyed, versus malignancy when that threshold is circumvented (Childs et al. 2015). Notably, cancer cells often exhibit gene-expression profiles resembling those of *embryonic* or *stem-like states*, underlining how fundamentally they diverge from the senescent-cell phenotype (West et al. 2018). In summary, senescence’s event horizon is a defining boundary in aging biology: most cells that cross it contribute to organismal aging, whereas those rare cells that dodge it can give rise to cancer.

Importantly, therapeutic targeting of cellular senescence has huge promise due to its **set-wide effects**. Preclinical studies have already demonstrated that therapies designed to selectively

eliminate senescent cells effectively reduce the burden across **multiple disease subsets simultaneously** (Zhu et al. 2015; Baker et al. 2016). Even modest senescent cell clearance can yield substantial improvements in healthspan and lifespan, reinforcing the role of cellular senescence as a causal nexus and primary target for intervention (Xu et al. 2018; Kirkland and Tchkonia 2020).

These findings reinforce the notion that cellular senescence is not merely correlative but **causal** in aging: it is the **key lever** in the system. By intervening at this fulcrum of aging’s event horizon, we can in principle modulate the course of multiple age-related diseases at once. Figure 4 schematically illustrates this concept, showing that an intervention at the senescence threshold could simultaneously tilt numerous disease trajectories toward healthier outcomes. In the sections that follow, we delve deeper into this strategy of “horizon engineering” - intentionally altering the senescence threshold and its consequences - to potentially transform aging from an inevitable decline into a more manageable, reversible condition.

Figure 4: “Horizon engineering” - targeting aging’s fulcrum. This figure introduces the strategy of **horizon engineering**, which treats cellular senescence as the main leverage point to alter aging’s course. We portray the **senescence threshold (event horizon)** as a dashed red boundary line: on the near (outer) side, cellular stress and damage are still reversible; on the far (inner) side, cells have become senescent and drive chronic pathology. We illustrate that by intervening at the horizon (depicted by a blue star), we can affect **multiple disease trajectories at once**. Arrows emanating from the intervention point span broadly across various age-related disease subsets (**N, V, D**

etc.) and comorbid conditions (set intersections), indicating a concurrent risk reduction in many conditions. In essence, we show senescence as a *fulcrum*: small changes at this upstream point yield amplified benefits downstream. This emphasizes that treating aging via its meta-disease mechanism (rather than one disease at a time) can compress morbidity across the board - a deliberate re-engineering of aging's "event horizon." Cancer (C) is depicted within A but largely outside S, reflecting malignancy's defining route of senescence-checkpoint bypass/escape.

3.2 Intervention as Horizon Engineering

Senescence's role as such a distinct biological switch makes it a uniquely actionable therapeutic target. Because it sits upstream of multiple disease categories, it functions as a **fulcrum of intervention**: modulating S affects broad swaths of A simultaneously. We refer to this strategic approach as **horizon engineering**.

In the long term, the ultimate goal of biogerontology is not merely to manage senescence but to **prevent its induction entirely** - that is, to avert the transition from reversible cellular stress to irreversible growth arrest, **abolishing the horizon altogether** (Figure 5 and Figure 6a). Realizing this will require **next-generation technologies** capable of maintaining or restoring youthful epigenetic and metabolic states. Approaches such as **gene editing** (Jing et al. 2025), **reprogramming (epigenetic rejuvenation)** (Kanherkar et al. 2014; Sarkar et al. 2020; Lu et al. 2020), **precision telomere modulation** (Jaskelioff et al. 2011), and **synthetic regulatory circuits** (Xie and Fussenegger 2018; Zhou et al. 2023; Godoy and Hao 2025) may eventually allow the senescence program to be reset or bypassed entirely, preserving cellular plasticity and regenerative potential indefinitely, leading to greatly extended lifespans. We term these **Horizon-Dissolving Operators (Ω^{HD})**: interventions that act on the **defining property of the horizon - irreversibility** - by targeting the regulatory constraints that make senescence effectively absorbing in state-space terms (Ross 1972; He and Sharpless 2017; Sagitov et al. 2024) (Figure 5 and Figure 6a). In stochastic-process language, an absorbing state is one that, once entered, is not exited under ordinary dynamics (Ross 1972). Formally, Ω^{HD} interventions alter the system's transition structure, converting what functions as an absorbing basin into a metastable or traversable region by relaxing the feedback constraints that enforce one-way entry. Yet these strategies remain at an early stage.

In the nearer term, progress is being made through **senotherapeutics** and **immune rejuvenation**, which together form an immediate practical frontier of translational geroscience. **Senotherapeutics** (Kim and Kim 2019; Kaur et al. 2020; Robbins et al. 2021; Zhang et al. 2022) are interventions that **target the biology of senescence**, whether by preventing its onset, modulating its phenotype, or eliminating senescent cells. We propose that these interventions can be organized along a **temporal axis** corresponding to the trajectory toward, across, and beyond the **senescence horizon**. **Senostatics** act *before*, **senomorphics** act *at*, and **senolytics** act *beyond* the horizon (Figure 5). **Immune rejuvenation** represents a fifth, system-level component of horizon engineering. Rather than acting directly on senescent cells, it **reactivates the body's endogenous clearance mechanisms** (Song et al. 2020), restoring immune surveillance and the

natural permeability of the horizon (Figure 5). It also includes cell replacement therapeutic strategies such as the engraftment of pluripotent stem cell-based hematopoietic stem cells or progenitors.

Figure 5: *Temporal staging of therapeutics around the senescence horizon.* This timeline figure shows five types of interventions relative to the point at which a cell becomes senescent (the **event horizon**, marked on the timeline as a dashed red line). At the top, **Horizon-Dissolving Operators (Ω^{HD})** (blue arrow), such as epigenetic reprogramming, act on the boundary itself, altering the regulatory architecture that defines/stabilizes senescence, weakening the irreversibility of the threshold and potentially *abolishing the horizon*. To the lower left, **Senostatics** (green arrow) such as telomerase activators are shown acting *before* cells cross into senescence - they keep stressed cells from converting to the senescent state (flattening the curve of senescence induction). Just over the horizon itself, **Senomorphics** (orange arrow) are depicted intervening at the moment a cell *becomes* senescent - they alter or dampen the senescent cell’s phenotype, especially reducing SASP factors, effectively “dimming” the deleterious “Hawking radiation” (continuing the analogy from black hole physics) without removing the cell. Further right of the horizon, **Senolytics** (red arrow) appear, targeting cells that have *already* become senescent - these interventions selectively destroy and clear those cells from tissues. Parallel to all these, we show **Immune Rejuvenation** (purple arrow) as a fifth modality: rather than acting directly on the timeline of a cell’s senescence process, immune therapies restore the body’s capacity to surveil and eliminate senescent cells **at any stage**. The coordinated display of these modalities supports our framework by showing a comprehensive, time-dependent approach to therapeutically modifying aging: dissolving the horizon, preventing senescence, mitigating its effects, removing its causes, and boosting natural clearance.

We now describe these modalities in more detail:

- **Senotherapeutics:** interventions that prevent senescence onset, modulate the senescent phenotype (e.g., SASP), or selectively eliminate senescent cells.
 - **Senostatics** prevent or delay the induction of senescence in stressed but viable cells by stabilizing redox balance, telomere integrity, and DNA repair capacity, thereby **blocking the horizon** and reducing the inflow into S (Figure 6b).
 - A special and highly important subgroup of senostatics are **telomerase activators**. Telomerase activation is a compelling meta-disease intervention because it targets an upstream constraint on tissue renewal and genome stability that underlies many aging phenotypes (Schellnegger et al. 2024). Progressive telomere dysfunction converts normal turnover into chronic DNA damage signaling, proliferative arrest, and cellular senescence, amplifying SASP-driven inflammation and eroding regenerative capacity across tissues. By restoring telomerase activity, proliferative reserves in stem and progenitor cells may be expanded, senescence burden reduced, and a central feed-forward driver of aging attenuated. In the meta-disease framework, this systems-level leverage distinguishes telomerase activation from downstream, disease-specific therapies, and should be a high focus, high yield target of research.
 - **Senomorphics** work further downstream on cells that have already crossed the horizon. They **“dim” the horizon** without removing the cells, thereby suppressing the inflammatory secretome, attenuating SASP-mediated signaling and thus blunting secondary damage. By suppressing SASP, they limit paracrine-mediated propagation of senescence (Figure 6b).
 - **Senolytics** shrink the interior of S by selectively clearing senescent cells. By selectively inducing apoptosis, they decompress tissue niches, restore regenerative capacity, and mitigate chronic inflammation. Even partial senescent cell ablation in animal models has shown systemic benefits, including improved cardiac function, increased exercise endurance, delayed onset of frailty, and extended healthspan (Figure 6c).
- **Immune rejuvenation strategies** seek to restore the *permeability* of the horizon by reactivating the body’s capacity to recognize and clear senescent cells, reversing the decline in immune surveillance that allows these cells to accumulate with age (Figure 6d). **Immune aging (I)** is not external to the senescent field but a **subset of it**, a manifestation of senescence within immune cells and their regulatory niches, known as immunosenescence (Tizazu et al. 2025). Yet **I** also **feeds back into S**: as immune aging advances, the system’s ability to remove senescent cells deteriorates, allowing them to persist and expand (Nguyen and Cho 2025). This reciprocal relationship forms a **self-reinforcing loop**, in which the senescent field enlarges through its own immune subsystem: $S \rightarrow I \rightarrow (\downarrow \text{clearance}) \rightarrow \uparrow S$ (Figure 7). Because **I** (immunosenescence) is

both a subset of the senescence-mediated changes, **S**, (since immune cells themselves undergo senescence) **and** an amplifier of senescence's effects (since immune decline lets senescent cells accumulate), effective **horizon engineering** must target both. Combining **reprogramming**, **senolytics** or **senostatic** and **senomorphic** agents with **immune age modulators** (e.g., **rapalogs**, **IL-7**, or **low-dose IL-2**) addresses senescence directly while restoring the immune system's ability to constrain it (Figure 7). Success should therefore be measured not only by reductions in multi-disease burden but also by improvements in **immune age composites**, **vaccine responsiveness**, and other functional readouts of **senescence-immunity coupling** (Qooja et al. 2025).

- An emerging extension is senescence-directed immunization: vaccines (and related antibody- or cell-based immunotherapies) that train the immune system to recognize senescence-enriched surface antigens ("**seno-antigens**") and **selectively eliminate senescent cells** - turning immune surveillance into a durable, specific senolytic mechanism (Figure 7). Proof-of-principle studies include peptide vaccination against CD153 to deplete senescent T cells and improve metabolic phenotypes in obese mice (Yoshida et al. 2020) and vaccination against GPNMB to reduce senescent burden and extend lifespan in progeroid mice (Suda et al. 2021). Dendritic-cell vaccine platforms delivering senescence antigens have also been reported (Cao et al. 2024; Ichim et al. 2025).

6a. Horizon-Dissolving Operators (Ω^{HD})

6b. Senostatics and Senomorphics

6c. Senolytics

6d. Immune Rejuvenation

Figure 6: Mechanisms of action for therapeutic strategies. Cell-state diagrams illustrate how treatments prevent, delay, or reverse progression across the senescence threshold. The “horizon” is drawn as a dashed red line. **(a) Horizon-Dissolving Operators (Ω^{HD}):** Interventions such as epigenetic reprogramming (blue DNA symbol) that act on the horizon itself, destabilizing the senescent attractor/threshold that maintains **S** and thereby reducing irreversibility (in principle permitting re-entry toward non-senescent states). **(b) Senostatics and Senomorphics:** Senostatics such as telomerase activators (green arrows) block the trajectory of cells approaching this line and “pull” them away from it (fewer cells become senescent over time). Senomorphics (orange arrows) are illustrated inside the horizon line, where senescent cells are present, but their harmful characteristics are **suppressed**. Senomorphics “dim” the horizon without removing the cells, thereby suppressing the inflammatory secretome, attenuating SASP-mediated signaling and thus blunting secondary damage. By suppressing SASP, they limit paracrine-mediated propagation of senescence. Together, these interventions reduce the influx into **S** and the intensity of each senescent cell’s impact. **(c) Senolytics:** senolytic drugs (red arrows) **clear senescent cells**. Before treatment, senescent cells accumulate; after senolytic treatment, far fewer remain. This removal, which **rejuvenates tissue microenvironments**, is shown as shrinking the event horizon (**S**) - the dashed red line becomes the inner dashed purple line. **(d) Immune Rejuvenation:** focuses on strategies that **enhance the immune system’s clearance of senescent cells**. Immune cells (purple arrows) are shown regaining activity and attacking senescent cells (depicted as targets on and across the event horizon). This effectively **reopens the closed senescence removal pathway** that occurs with age. Collectively, the panels show complementary levers: boundary destabilization (Ω^{HD}), prevention, phenotypic damping, targeted elimination, and restored immune clearance.

Figure 7: Recursive coupling of cellular senescence (*S*) and immune aging (*I*) within the meta-disease framework. Upstream molecular insults - including DNA damage, oxidative stress, and telomere attrition - drive cells across the senescence event horizon (*S*), shown as the dashed red line. Once established, senescent cells (light blue) generate age-related diseases and simultaneously induce immunosenescence (*I*), represented as a nested light orange subset within *S*. Immunosenescence (*I*) arises as a direct manifestation of senescence within immune cells and their regulatory niches, leading to impaired immune surveillance and reduced clearance of senescent cells. This loss of clearance, together with inflammaging, **feeds back to further expand the senescent field** (red triangle and curved arrow), creating a self-reinforcing loop ($S \rightarrow I \rightarrow \downarrow \text{clearance} \rightarrow \uparrow S$). The blue triangle and curved arrow denote the forward influence of senescence on immune aging, while the red triangle and arrow highlight feedback amplification from immune dysfunction *back into* the senescent compartment. We also show an enlarged cancer subset, *C*, caused by the resultant failing immune response. **Horizon engineering strategies**, including reprogramming, senolytics, senomorphic-senostatics, and immune rejuvenation approaches act at multiple points in this loop to dissolve the horizon, restore permeability, reduce senescent burden, and re-establish immune-mediated constraint of senescence. Senescence-directed immunization (seno-antigen vaccines/related immunotherapies, green arrow) is shown acting on the $I \rightarrow \text{clearance}$ link to **restore** immune-mediated removal of senescent cells, **opposing the feedback amplification that expands *S***.

Together, these interventions act as Ω_s operators: they shrink the senescent subset *S* and reduce the measure or impact of the senescence-mediated region, thereby contracting risk across multiple subsets. They do not merely mask symptoms; they **rewire the underlying risk architecture of aging itself**.

3.3 Translational Implications and Empirical Validation

The biological and therapeutic centrality of senescence provides **empirical support** for the aging-as-meta-disease framework. If senescence causally mediates multiple age-related pathologies, then interventions that reduce senescence should yield **multi-domain benefit** - a pattern already supported by senolytic and senostatic studies in preclinical models (Xu et al. 2018; Zhang et al. 2022). From a systems biology perspective, these findings suggest that aging is not a diffuse, unchangeable process, but a **modifiable state-space** with measurable inputs and outputs (Cohen et al. 2022).

Computationally, this architecture naturally lends itself to latent-variable modeling that **integrates many biomarkers at once** (Argelaguet et al. 2020). Senescence can be treated as a latent mediator linking upstream multi-omic damage signatures to downstream disease risk. Modern machine-learning approaches, particularly latent-state models and causal representation learning, can learn low-dimensional embeddings from integrated omic, imaging, and clinical data (Scholkopf et al. 2021), yielding a compact “senescence coordinate” (senescence-mediated burden within the broader aging state-space) and an associated “distance-to-horizon” metric. A position-aware biomarker portfolio, including markers of identity (e.g., p16^{INK4a}, p21^{CIP1}), SASP profiling, and systems-level readouts (e.g., fibrosis imaging, immune clearance indices), can be used to estimate these coordinates longitudinally and test intervention effects (Ovadya et al. 2018; Zhang et al. 2022; Maus et al. 2023).

This architecture yields **falsifiable predictions**: reducing **S** should delay disease onset across multiple subsets (Baker et al. 2016; Zhang et al. 2022); the breadth of benefit should scale with the magnitude and distribution of reduction (Baker et al. 2016); and cancer should respond differently given its largely disjoint relationship with **S** (Zhang et al. 2022).

We now shift to implementation: the focus, metrics, trial designs, data infrastructure, and coordination mechanisms needed to operationalize aging-as-meta-disease in research and clinical development.

4 Research and Implementation Roadmap

Building on the premise that aging is a meta-disease whose downstream pathologies are largely generated by the senescence-mediated regime **S**, **we should treat S as the primary therapeutic target**. Our highest-leverage translational strategy is therefore to **identify S, quantify it, and relentlessly contract it** - iteratively and at scale - toward the functional elimination of *pathologic persistence* (while preserving some beneficial, transient senescence programs). Metaphorically, **S** is the system’s Achilles heel, a vulnerable choke point where a focused intervention can propagate into broad downstream effects across many disease subsets. **Cancer remains a special-case**

trajectory and requires parallel, continuous surveillance as we manipulate senescence defenses.

Operationalizing this premise turns translation into a coordination problem with a clear goal: **the majority of the roadmap should serve the goal of shrinking S (and/or neutralizing its SASP-mediated amplification), safely, measurably, and iteratively**. The sequence below therefore prioritizes (1) computational representations that make S legible and targetable, (2) surveillance systems that measure movement into/out of S across tissues, (3) intervention platforms whose primary aim is contraction of S, and (4) phased deployment that scales S-reducing practice without widening disparities.

4.1 Computational Modeling of the Meta-Disease Architecture

Translating the meta-disease paradigm into practice will require computational models that treat aging as a high-dimensional state-space, **estimate the tissue-specific extent/distribution of the senescence-mediated regime S**, and predict which downstream disease domains are consolidating. A useful abstraction is a learned landscape (Figure 8), in which tissue identity and multi-omic “damage-and-response” coordinates define position, and disease states appear as **tissue-conditioned attractors** (Huang 2009; Cohen et al. 2022) whose depth reflects the emergence and expansion of S. More specifically, the horizontal axes could depict low-dimensional embedding with tissue identity and damage coordinates. The vertical axis (and colormap) could encode **senescence burden/activity**, i.e., the **magnitude** of the senescence-mediated regime $S \subset A$. Here, senescence would be visualized as **attractor depth** (more negative/deeper and red = higher senescent burden), and the **basins** represent **tissue-conditioned disease attractors** - domains where senescence has consolidated sufficiently to generate stable downstream pathology (and, by extension, predictable overlap/multimorbidity when multiple basins deepen across tissues) (Figure 8).

Crucially, the goal is not a vague risk score, but a detailed mapping that: (1) locates individuals in state-space (from tissue- and cell-derived measurements), (2) **quantifies S as a primary latent variable (burden, distribution, and activity/SASP output)**, and (3) forecasts which disease domains are forming as senescence becomes established across tissues. In effect, the model should be engineered so that **contracting S is the central controllable axis** - the quantity we learn to estimate robustly, move intentionally, and validate against clinical outcomes (Figure 8).

Figure 8: Learned “senescence landscape” of the meta-disease state-space (*A*). This schematic illustrates how aging-as-meta-disease can be represented as a **low-dimensional, interpretable landscape** learned from multimodal data. The horizontal axes depict an embedding of the universal aging state-space **A**: **cell/tissue identity** (Principal component 1-like, [PC1-like]) on the x-axis and a **compressed aging/damage-response coordinate** (Principal Component 2-like [PC2-like]) on the y-axis. The vertical axis (and colormap) encodes **senescence burden/activity**, i.e., the **magnitude** of the senescence-mediated regime $S \subset A$. Here, senescence is visualized as **attractor depth** (more negative/deeper and redder = higher senescent burden), and the **basins** represent **tissue-conditioned disease attractors** - domains where senescence has consolidated sufficiently to generate stable downstream pathology (and, by extension, predictable overlap/multimorbidity when multiple basins deepen across tissues). Contours on the base plane indicate iso-depth structure and basin geometry. This framing makes the translational goal explicit: if **S is the causal generating set**, then successful gerotherapeutics should **shallow these basins by contracting S** (and/or neutralizing SASP-mediated amplification), ideally pushing persistent, pathologic senescent burden toward **functional elimination**. In practice, A.I./representation-learning models can be trained to (1) locate individuals on this landscape from tissue-, blood-, physiologic-, and imaging-derived features, (2) estimate tissue-specific **S** distribution, and (3) quantify whether interventions measurably **move trajectories away from disease attractors**. Critically, the Z-dimension must be anchored to **tissue-resolved senescence measurement** (e.g., senescence-targeted PET where feasible - see Figure 9), with orthogonal structural/functional readouts (e.g., MRI and organ function) providing complementary validation.

Critically, the landscape’s vertical (Z) dimension - attractor depth as a function of tissue senescence burden - **must be anchored to real-world, in vivo, tissue-resolved measurement**, most directly through the further evolution of senescence-targeted positron emission tomography (PET) (Figure

9), with magnetic resonance imaging (MRI) and other emerging organ-level readouts providing complementary structural and functional validation. By “**Senescence PET**,” we mean radiotracers that preferentially accumulate in senescent programs (most notably SA- β -gal-activated galactoside strategies, with alternatives targeting senescence-associated byproducts such as lipofuscin), yielding repeatable, quantitative, **organ-resolved proxies for senescent burden or activity** (Brickute et al. 2022; Suryadevara et al. 2024; Xiang et al. 2024). Because senescence markers are heterogeneous and context-dependent, uptake should be interpreted as a probabilistic proxy and calibrated against multimarker tissue validation, enabling a tissue-specific senescence latent variable whose scale is tied to tracer uptake/kinetics. As multi-probe panels and complementary modalities (including SA- β -gal-responsive MR agents) mature, **whole-body senescence “maps”** could become system-level trial endpoints, supporting **stratification by the distribution of S**, early on-treatment confirmation of **senescence contraction**, and mechanistic linkage to **downstream shifts in multimorbidity trajectories** (Nernekli et al. 2025; Gagliardi et al. 2025). Although not yet clinically standardized, this field is developing rapidly.

Figure 9: *Conceptual whole-body PET-style map of relative senescent cell burden with joint-dominant distribution.* A human silhouette is overlaid with a schematic “senescence PET” signal (heatmap), where warmer colors (red) indicate higher modeled tracer retention / inferred senescent cell load and cooler colors (blue) indicate lower relative burden. Hotspots are placed to illustrate an arthritis-like pattern in this example, with prominent signal at major joints (e.g., shoulders, elbows, wrists, hips, knees, and ankles), with comparatively low signal across most trunk soft tissues. The

color bar indicates **normalized relative senescent cell burden (arbitrary units)** and is intended to illustrate the *type* of whole-body readout that senescence-targeted imaging could provide; the image is **illustrative of current and evolving technology** and not derived from an individual participant or patient scan.

4.2 Coordinated Surveillance and Metrics

Building on the computational representation of the meta-disease architecture outlined above, we envision a comprehensive surveillance infrastructure that continuously links real-world health data to individualized **digital twins** (i.e., longitudinal computational patient-state models updated by multimodal data) (Pusparum et al. 2025). The goal is not merely prediction, but *measurement*: position-aware biomarkers and composite endpoints that quantify “movement within aging space **A**” - that is, changes in overall aging burden rather than changes in any single disease. For example, clinical trials would prioritize multi-domain composite outcomes (such as time-to-first event across cardiovascular, neurodegenerative, metabolic, and other disease categories) to gauge broad efficacy (Rolland et al. 2023). These metrics, coupled with ICD-11 aging-related codes (Khaltourina et al. 2020) will ensure that upstream benefits are visible to regulators and payers, aligning research outputs with clinical and reimbursement frameworks.

Within an A.I.-enabled framework, surveillance metrics need not be limited to static biomarker thresholds. Instead, position-aware metrics can be derived from computational aging models that estimate an individual’s location and velocity within the aging state-space. Such measures quantify movement toward or away from the senescence horizon, enabling early detection of accelerated aging trajectories before overt disease manifests. Composite endpoints - already motivated clinically - thus acquire a formal computational meaning: they reflect contraction or expansion of high-risk regions within set **S** rather than isolated disease events.

In parallel, open data standards and federated cohorts will enable multi-layer data reporting (linking outcomes to mechanistic layers) and continuous refinement of predictive models, creating a feedback loop between **biomarker development** and real-world outcomes. With this measurement infrastructure in place, the next step is to test therapies that deliberately reshape the senescence-mediated region of aging space.

4.3 Intervention Toolkit and Horizon Engineering

With cellular senescence as the causal nexus, implementation should center on interventions that “engineer” the senescence horizon (Section 3.2), evaluated using composite morbidity endpoints and biomarker-guided target engagement readouts (Kritchevsky et al. 2025). But the strategic emphasis should be explicit: **the purpose of the toolkit is to shrink S** - to reduce the prevalence, persistence, and downstream influence of senescent cells across tissues - while preserving safety and tissue integrity.

Early trials should prioritize adaptive, platform designs (Serra et al. 2022) capable of testing combinations of Horizon-Dissolving Operators (Ω^{HD}), senostatics, senomorphics, senolytics, immune rejuvenation and senescence-directed immunotherapies (including vaccination approaches), with pre-specified safety monitoring and stopping rules. The platform logic would be especially well-matched to the “systematic (but safe) pursuit” of **S** because it would enable rapid iteration on a simple criterion: **does the regimen demonstrably reduce S in the intended tissues, and does that translate into slower accumulation of disease-domain attractor depth?**

Because cancer follows an exceptional route within **A**, oncology surveillance should be embedded in trial monitoring when manipulating senescence defenses, alongside vigilance for potential harms such as impaired wound healing or immune dysfunction (Lorenzo et al. 2023). Practically, this means the clinical development program should be framed as **aggressively anti-senescence but clinically conservative on safety**: we should seek to eliminate *pathologic, persistent* senescence as a driver of degeneration, without destabilizing tumor-suppressive safeguards or essential repair programs.

4.4 Phased Deployment

The roadmap could proceed in phases to translate these advances into practice, moving from measurement and validation, to early deployment, to system-wide integration.

An initial **Launch phase (0 - 2 years)** would establish the foundation: developing a standardized biomarker kit, validating multi-domain composite outcome measures, initiating the first platform trials for aging interventions, and piloting the use of ICD-11 aging-related codes in clinical data (Khaltourina et al. 2020; Stambler et al. 2022).

A **Build phase (3 - 7 years)** would expand these efforts through accelerated regulatory pathways for senescence-targeting therapies, outcomes-based reimbursement models (e.g., contracts rewarding delayed multimorbidity onset), community-level delivery programs, and pilot projects designed to prevent widened disparities (see Section 5.3) (Bakula et al. 2018; Bystritskaya 2025).

Finally, a **Scale phase (7 - 15 years)** would integrate aging interventions into guidelines and health systems worldwide, supported by continuous learning networks and international procurement agreements that reinvest the resulting longevity dividend into public health (World Health Organization 2009; Barker et al. 2015). Governance should be orchestrated via an international consortium, e.g., an **International Meta-Disease Implementation Consortium**, to harmonize standards, coordinate stakeholders, and maintain an evidence-update loop across research, clinical, and policy domains.

Together, these phases operationalize a learn-as-you-scale pathway for aging interventions, with Section 5.3 below detailing the justice, proportionality, and data-governance constraints that should govern deployment.

Having outlined a practical roadmap for measuring, testing, and deploying meta-disease interventions, the next question is what institutional scaffolding is required to make this feasible at scale. Accordingly, in Section 5 we shift from implementation mechanics to the **regulatory, economic, and ethical frameworks** needed to align approval pathways, reimbursement incentives, and equity safeguards with therapies that act upstream on aging biology rather than on single diseases.

5 Regulatory, Economic, and Ethical Implications

Formally defining aging as a meta-disease would provide the regulatory and economic scaffolding needed to integrate geroscience into mainstream biomedical practice. Existing frameworks, including those of the Food and Drug Administration and European Medicines Agency, are oriented toward discrete indications, which **effectively disadvantages interventions that target upstream, systemic mechanisms of aging** (Tournas and Marchant 2019; Rolland et al. 2023). As a result, geroscience approaches often fall outside traditional approval categories, forcing developers to fit system-level interventions into single-disease indications (Muscedere et al. 2025). This creates a **misalignment between biological causality and regulatory structure**. As a result, there is a growing need for regulatory reform or the creation of new approval pathways that accommodate interventions aimed at delaying or modifying aging itself as a causal driver of multiple chronic conditions (Tournas and Marchant 2019; Muscedere et al. 2025).

Accordingly, this section outlines (1) a plausible regulatory logic for geroprotective indications, (2) reimbursement architectures that internalize the longevity dividend, and (3) ethical guardrails, especially justice and data governance, needed to prevent translation from widening disparities.

5.1 Regulations

Within a meta-disease paradigm, regulators could establish a **geroprotective approval pathway**, in which efficacy is demonstrated through mechanistic and **composite endpoints** that capture multisystem benefit rather than single-disease modification (Marzetti et al. 2025; Muscedere et al. 2025). Trials such as **Targeting Aging with Metformin (TAME)** exemplify this logic: composite endpoints - time to incidence of any among several age-associated conditions - operationalize aging as a quantifiable substrate of morbidity (Barzilai et al. 2016). Embedding such trials within ICD-11 frameworks would further enable aging-related mechanisms to be codable in regulatory submissions and clinical data systems (Kuan et al. 2021), supporting label language, comparability across trials, and post-marketing traceability of geroprotective efficacy.

Aging's reclassification would also justify **mechanism-based conditional approvals**, analogous to accelerated pathways in oncology. Surrogate endpoints such as validated **epigenetic clocks**, **senescence load indices**, or **proteomic aging signatures** could serve as interim measures for conditional authorization, with full approval contingent upon demonstrated reduction in composite morbidity (Marzetti et al. 2025). More speculatively, regulators might introduce **composite aging clearances**, approvals grounded in a demonstrable delay in multimorbidity trajectories rather than disease-specific incidence curves (Muscedere et al. 2025). Such constructs would align regulatory evaluation with biological reality, acknowledging that upstream intervention in aging mechanisms generates distributed, system-level effects.

5.2 Economics

Economically, this reframing would restructure both innovation incentives and health-system valuation. Recognizing aging as a treatable meta-disease expands the addressable market from specific patient subpopulations to the entirety of aging cohorts, thereby catalyzing investment in **geroprotective drug development** (Zhavoronkov and Bhullar 2015). It also permits actuarial modeling of the **longevity dividend**, the welfare gain produced by delaying biological aging. Empirical analyses estimate global returns on the order of US \$38 trillion per one-year delay and **US \$367 trillion for a ten-year delay**, dwarfing the economic impact of eliminating any single disease (Goldman 2016; Scott et al. 2021). These figures reflect compounded benefits from reduced morbidity, extended workforce participation, and decreased long-term care expenditures.

To internalize such gains, novel **reimbursement architectures** will be required. **Outcomes-based or horizon-linked contracts** could tie payment to measurable extensions in disease-free survival or maintenance of intrinsic capacity, distributing the longevity dividend among payers, providers, and innovators (Kerdelmidis and Fiorenza 2023; Yoshimori 2025). Governments might deploy **advance market commitments** or longevity-linked bonds to underwrite early-stage development, while insurers could incorporate **aging-burden indices** derived from ICD-11 qualifiers into risk adjustment and premium structures. Over time, health systems could transition toward **preventive longevity management**, a model in which success is defined not by treating discrete diseases, but by measurably slowing biological aging across populations (Scott et al. 2021; Commission for a Global Roadmap for Healthy Longevity and National Academy of Medicine 2022).

In aggregate, recognizing aging as a meta-disease would **harmonize regulatory logic with biological causality** and align economic incentives with public-health objectives. It would transform aging from an abstract risk factor into a quantifiable, intervenable process, creating the foundation for a new class of therapies, a coherent framework for their approval, and an economic rationale for their universal adoption.

5.3 Ethics

Framing aging as a modifiable, treatable meta-disease raises deep ethical questions but, on balance, **strengthens the moral case for intervention**. If aging is the principal upstream driver of morbidity, suffering, and dependency, then **failing to act where effective solutions exist would contravene beneficence - the duty to prevent harm and promote good** (Harris 2004; Lucke et al. 2010). Because combating aging is ethically continuous with curing disease, **delaying death through geroprotective intervention is itself a life-saving act** (Harris 2004). Historical analyses of medical innovation further suggest that paradigm-shifting causal frameworks are often slow to gain acceptance despite clear downstream benefit, indicating that delayed adoption can carry ethical consequences (Csoka 2016). In this view, extending healthy life is not enhancement but therapy, and the standard bioethical pillars - beneficence, non-maleficence, autonomy, and justice - apply directly to longevity technologies (Lucke et al. 2010), requiring both scientific advancement and careful mitigation of risks.

Justice, in particular, makes equity central to responsible translation. Without deliberate safeguards, longevity interventions **could widen health disparities**, making extended vitality a privilege of the wealthy (Saliev and Singh 2025). Masny argues that justice demands a fair opportunity for a “**complete life**,” implying that access to therapies delaying aging should not track socioeconomic status (Masny 2023). Lucke et al. similarly caution that novel biotechnologies often debut as elite services and emphasize public investment and inclusive trial participation to prevent longevity gaps between nations and social classes (Lucke et al. 2010).

Accordingly, **ethical oversight must be ingrained at each stage of translation**: principles of therapeutic justice and proportionality should guide trial design, inclusion, endpoints, and post-trial access, while equity-by-design measures, such as tiered pricing, regional manufacturing, and broad licensing, help ensure global inclusion rather than widening longevity gaps (Amuthavalli Thiyagarajan et al. 2022; Commission for a Global Roadmap for Healthy Longevity and National Academy of Medicine 2022; Peng et al. 2023; Saliev and Singh 2025). Robust data governance frameworks, including dynamic patient consent, privacy-preserving analytics, and audit trails for algorithmic decisions, are likewise necessary to protect individual rights as large-scale health data drive these innovations (Ahmed et al. 2025; Welzel et al. 2025).

Finally, classifying aging as a meta-disease **need not pathologize older adults**; it targets an upstream biological process to justify prevention and treatment, analogous to managing hypertension or hyperlipidemia. Embedding proportionality safeguards, equity-by-design levers, and rights-preserving data governance **strengthens the likelihood that reclassification reduces, rather than amplifies, disparities**.

With these ethical implications in view, we now close by returning to the paper's central claim: what aging is, how it generates disease, and what it implies for the purpose of medicine when we target upstream architecture rather than downstream fragments.

6 Synthesis and the Purpose and Future of Medicine

6.1 *Synthesis of the Meta-Disease Framework*

For most of human history, the hope of overcoming aging carried metaphysical connotations - sometimes expressed as alchemy's elixir, more often as a philosophical refusal to accept that decline is the final outcome of life. We argue that the aspiration can now be stated formally. The familiar dispute - aging as "natural" versus aging as "disease" - persists because it conflates levels of description. In Hegelian terms, the opposition sublates into a higher-order synthesis: aging is universal in its presence yet pathogenic in its causal role. It is not a discrete disease among others, but a **meta-disease** - the generative causal architecture from which late-life pathologies arise. Metaphorically, aging is the **soil in which disease takes root**.

We formalized this architecture through a set-theoretic nosology: aging defines the universal set **A**, the total age-related state-space, while disease families appear as overlapping subsets: cardiovascular disease (**V**), neurodegeneration (**N**), and even structural (**T**) and cosmetic (**K**) phenotypes historically dismissed as "normal aging." Multimorbidity becomes predictable geometry: intersections are expected because subsets share a common ontological container. The framework becomes causally intelligible when **cellular senescence (S)** is treated as the **generating subset** within **A** - an **event-horizon**-like threshold beyond which stable arrest and the SASP convert local damage into persistent, propagating dysfunction. As **S** expands across tissues it populates and enlarges multiple downstream disease domains, while cancer retains a special position (**C** \subset **A**) insofar as malignancy is defined by escape from the senescence barrier.

From these foundations we derived a translational strategy termed horizon engineering. Interventions can dissolve the horizon, reduce inflow into **S** (senostatics), dampen SASP-driven amplification (senomorphics), contract **S** through selective clearance (senolytics), and restore endogenous constraint mechanisms through immune rejuvenation. Read out with position-aware biomarkers and composite endpoints, our program treats aging as a modifiable state-space - and makes the central clinical objective explicit: to safely measure, pursue, and shrink **S**. Once medicine can act upstream on the architecture that generates late-life disease, the remaining question is no longer only technical but teleological: toward what end should this power be used?

6.2 *Implications for the Purpose and Future of Medicine*

That question is ultimately about **purpose**: what medicine is for, and what a human life is aiming at (Pellegrino 2005). If aging is understood as an upstream deformation of biological regulation,

mediated by cellular senescence that causes all downstream age-related diseases, then medicine's role should refocus from episodic repair toward protection of integrity across time. In Aristotelian terms, this is the defense of **entelechy** - the capacity of an organism to remain coherently itself while actualizing its potentials. Aging, so construed, is not merely time passing but the **progressive erosion** of that capacity. To intervene upstream is therefore not simply to delay death, but to preserve the biological conditions under which **eudaimonia** - a life of sustained agency, relationship, creativity, contribution, and meaning - remains possible across an extended arc (Ryff 2014; Martela and Ryan 2023).

This perspective aligns with modern accounts of human motivation. Psychological development does not culminate in basic survival or comfort, but in **self-transcendence**: the pursuit of meaning and contribution beyond the self (Maslow 1954; Koltko-Rivera 2006). Extending healthy lifespan expands the space in which such higher aims can be realized, a view supported by evidence that many individuals expect additional healthy years to enable deeper relationships, sustained creativity, and greater accomplishment (Lucke et al. 2010). In this sense, longevity science is not only a biomedical project but a humanistic one.

To pursue these ends, medicine must become a discipline of trajectories: mapping and **preventing decline before failure consolidates**.

How medicine pursues such aims is shaped, in part, by language. Linguistic relativity informs us that words shape perception: **the categories we conceptualize become the categories we measure and treat**. Defining aging as a meta-disease is therefore a **deliberate act of re-framing** that renders aging's causal architecture visible as a **primary** object of intervention, while making individual diseases downstream manifestations.

In this respect, naming aging a meta-disease constitutes a paradigm shift in a Kuhnian sense (Kuhn 1962): a change in what medicine treats as fundamental - what it explains first, and **what it acts on first**. The Copernican revolution, after all, was not just a triumph of new instruments, but a **change of perception** that made familiar observations make more sense. So too here: aging's causal architecture becomes the **center** of medicine, and **individual diseases its satellites**. **A.I. can play an important role here** by operationalizing the meta-disease paradigm: integrating heterogeneous longitudinal measurements, inferring latent aging state (including proxies for the distribution/activity of **S** within **A**) and testing whether interventions measurably shift trajectories over time (Argelaguet et al. 2020; Scholkopf et al. 2021).

Finally, a big-picture framing: even without invoking teleology, life is characterized by directional work - **maintaining form against entropy** (Schrödinger 1944), sustaining coherence amid perturbation, and generating higher-order capacities from lower-order substrates (Mayr 1974; Kauffman 1993). In that light, targeting aging's causal architecture **aligns medicine with a deep property of living systems**: the preservation of organized complexity. What alchemy once

expressed as longing, this framework recasts as blueprint: the prospect that the causes of late-life disease can be mapped upstream and progressively pushed back.

Just as germ theory reorganized nineteenth-century medicine by revealing a single upstream cause behind many different infections, *aging-as-meta-disease* can reorganize modern medicine by revealing an upstream cause behind multimorbidity. If germ theory taught us how to protect life, and molecular biology how to decode it, the meta-disease paradigm teaches how to preserve its **telos**: by sustaining the biological conditions of entelechy, eudaimonia, and self-transcendence that **defy time**.

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References

- Ahmed MM, Okesanya OJ, Oweidat M, et al (2025) The ethics of data mining in healthcare: challenges, frameworks, and future directions. *BioData Min* 18:47. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s13040-025-00461-w>
- Aliper AM, Csoka AB, Buzdin A, et al (2015) Signaling pathway activation drift during aging: Hutchinson-Gilford Progeria Syndrome fibroblasts are comparable to normal middle-age and old-age cells. *Aging* 26–37. <https://doi.org/10.18632/aging.100717>
- Al-Juhany A (2025) Why We Should Not Characterize Aging as a Disease. *Philos Med* 6:. <https://doi.org/10.5195/pom.2025.238>
- Alvarez-Galvez J, Vegas-Lozano E (2022) Discovery and classification of complex multimorbidity patterns: unravelling chronicity networks and their social profiles. *Sci Rep* 12:20004. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41598-022-23617-8>
- Amuthavalli Thiyagarajan J, Mikton C, Harwood RH, et al (2022) The UN Decade of healthy ageing: strengthening measurement for monitoring health and wellbeing of older people. *Age Ageing* 51:afac147. <https://doi.org/10.1093/ageing/afac147>
- Argelaguet R, Arnol D, Bredikhin D, et al (2020) MOFA+: a statistical framework for comprehensive integration of multi-modal single-cell data. *Genome Biol* 21:111. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s13059-020-02015-1>
- Baker DJ, Childs BG, Durik M, et al (2016) Naturally occurring p16Ink4a-positive cells shorten healthy lifespan. *Nature* 530:184–189. <https://doi.org/10.1038/nature16932>
- Bakula D, Aliper AM, Mamoshina P, et al (2018) Aging and drug discovery. *Aging* 10:3079–3088. <https://doi.org/10.18632/aging.101646>
- Barabási A-L, Gulbahce N, Loscalzo J (2011) Network medicine: a network-based approach to human disease. *Nat Rev Genet* 12:56–68. <https://doi.org/10.1038/nrg2918>
- Barker PM, Reid A, Schall MW (2015) A framework for scaling up health interventions: lessons from large-scale improvement initiatives in Africa. *Implement Sci* 11:12. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s13012-016-0374-x>
- Barzilai N, Crandall JP, Kritchevsky SB, Espeland MA (2016) Metformin as a Tool to Target Aging. *Cell Metab* 23:1060–1065. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cmet.2016.05.011>
- Bateson G (1972) *Steps to an Ecology of Mind*. University of Chicago Press
- Bhatia-Dey N, Kanherkar RR, Stair SE, et al (2016) Cellular Senescence as the Causal Nexus of Aging. *Front Genet* 7:. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fgene.2016.00013>
- Binstock RH, Fishman JR, Johnson TE (2006) Anti-Aging Medicine and Science. In: *Handbook of Aging and the Social Sciences*. Elsevier, pp 436–455

- Boorse C (1977) Health as a Theoretical Concept. *Philos Sci* 44:542–573.
<https://doi.org/10.1086/288768>
- Brickute D, Chen C, Braga M, et al (2022) Design, synthesis, and evaluation of a novel PET imaging agent targeting lipofuscin in senescent cells. *RSC Adv* 12:26372–26381.
<https://doi.org/10.1039/D2RA04535D>
- Bulterijs S, Hull RS, Björk VCE, Roy AG (2015) It is time to classify biological aging as a disease. *Front Genet* 6:. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fgene.2015.00205>
- Bystritskaya Y (2025) From biomarkers to balance sheets: How longevity therapeutics could reshape health economics. *Longev. Technol.*
- Campisi J, d’Adda Di Fagagna F (2007) Cellular senescence: when bad things happen to good cells. *Nat Rev Mol Cell Biol* 8:729–740. <https://doi.org/10.1038/nrm2233>
- Cao Y, Du X, Yu J, et al (2024) Seno-antigen-pulsed dendritic cell vaccine induce anti-aging immunity to improve adipose tissue senescence and metabolic abnormalities. *Biomed Pharmacother* 179:117433. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.biopha.2024.117433>
- Caplan A (2015) How Can Aging Be Thought of as Anything Other Than a Disease? In: Schramme T, Edwards S (eds) *Handbook of the Philosophy of Medicine*. Springer Netherlands, Dordrecht, pp 1–8
- Cesari M, Araujo De Carvalho I, Amuthavalli Thiyagarajan J, et al (2018) Evidence for the Domains Supporting the Construct of Intrinsic Capacity. *J Gerontol Ser A* 73:1653–1660. <https://doi.org/10.1093/gerona/gly011>
- Childs BG, Durik M, Baker DJ, Van Deursen JM (2015) Cellular senescence in aging and age-related disease: from mechanisms to therapy. *Nat Med* 21:1424–1435.
<https://doi.org/10.1038/nm.4000>
- Cohen AA, Ferrucci L, Fülöp T, et al (2022) A complex systems approach to aging biology. *Nat Aging* 2:580–591. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s43587-022-00252-6>
- Collado M, Serrano M (2010) Senescence in tumours: evidence from mice and humans. *Nat Rev Cancer* 10:51–57. <https://doi.org/10.1038/nrc2772>
- Commission for a Global Roadmap for Healthy Longevity, National Academy of Medicine (2022) *Global Roadmap for Healthy Longevity*. National Academies Press, Washington, D.C.
- Csoka AB (2016) Innovation in medicine: Ignaz the reviled and Egas the regaled. *Med Health Care Philos* 19:163–168. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11019-015-9678-x>
- Cummings SR, Kritchevsky SB (2022) Endpoints for geroscience clinical trials: health outcomes, biomarkers, and biologic age. *GeroScience* 44:2925–2931.
<https://doi.org/10.1007/s11357-022-00671-8>

- De Grey ADNJ, Rae M (2007) Ending aging: the rejuvenation breakthroughs that could reverse human aging in our lifetime, 1. ed. St. Martin's Press, New York
- De Winter G (2015) Aging as Disease. *Med Health Care Philos* 18:237–243.
<https://doi.org/10.1007/s11019-014-9600-y>
- Franceschi C, Garagnani P, Morsiani C, et al (2018) The Continuum of Aging and Age-Related Diseases: Common Mechanisms but Different Rates. *Front Med* 5:61.
<https://doi.org/10.3389/fmed.2018.00061>
- Fulop T, Larbi A, Khalil A, et al (2019) Are We Ill Because We Age? *Front Physiol* 10:1508.
<https://doi.org/10.3389/fphys.2019.01508>
- Gagliardi A, Migliari S, Guercio A, et al (2025) Emerging Radioligands as Tools to Track Multi-Organ Senescence. *Diagnostics* 15:2518. <https://doi.org/10.3390/diagnostics15192518>
- Gladyshev TV, Gladyshev VN (2016) A Disease or Not a Disease? Aging As a Pathology. *Trends Mol Med* 22:995–996. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.molmed.2016.09.009>
- Godoy P, Hao N (2025) Design principles of gene circuits for longevity. *Trends Cell Biol* 35:840–853. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.tcb.2025.02.006>
- Goldman D (2016) The Economic Promise of Delayed Aging. *Cold Spring Harb Perspect Med* 6:a025072. <https://doi.org/10.1101/cshperspect.a025072>
- Goldman DP, Cutler D, Rowe JW, et al (2013) Substantial Health And Economic Returns From Delayed Aging May Warrant A New Focus For Medical Research. *Health Aff (Millwood)* 32:1698–1705. <https://doi.org/10.1377/hlthaff.2013.0052>
- Halmos PR (1960) *Naive Set Theory*. Springer
- Hamilton WD (1966) The moulding of senescence by natural selection. *J Theor Biol* 12:12–45.
[https://doi.org/10.1016/0022-5193\(66\)90184-6](https://doi.org/10.1016/0022-5193(66)90184-6)
- Harris J (2004) Immortal Ethics. *Ann N Y Acad Sci* 1019:527–534.
<https://doi.org/10.1196/annals.1297.098>
- Hasin Y, Seldin M, Lusis A (2017) Multi-omics approaches to disease. *Genome Biol* 18:83.
<https://doi.org/10.1186/s13059-017-1215-1>
- He S, Sharpless NE (2017) Senescence in Health and Disease. *Cell* 169:1000–1011.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cell.2017.05.015>
- Hegel GWF (1807) *Phänomenologie des Geistes*. Joseph Anton Goebhardt, Bamberg und Würzburg
- Hegel GWF (1812) *Wissenschaft der Logik. Erster Teil: Die objektive Logik. Erstes Buch: Die Lehre vom Sein*. Johann Leonhard Schrag, Nürnberg

- Huang S (2009) Reprogramming cell fates: reconciling rarity with robustness. *BioEssays* 31:546–560. <https://doi.org/10.1002/bies.200800189>
- Ichim TE, Lopes G, Reznik R, et al (2025) Reduction of solid tumors by senescent cell immunization. *J Transl Med* 23:1365. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12967-025-07393-3>
- Izaks GJ, Westendorp RG (2003) Ill or just old? Towards a conceptual framework of the relation between ageing and disease. *BMC Geriatr* 3:7. <https://doi.org/10.1186/1471-2318-3-7>
- Jaskelioff M, Muller FL, Paik J-H, et al (2011) Telomerase reactivation reverses tissue degeneration in aged telomerase-deficient mice. *Nature* 469:102–106. <https://doi.org/10.1038/nature09603>
- Jing Y, Ren J, Qu J, Liu G-H (2025) Gene therapy strategies for aging intervention. *Cell Insight* 4:100254. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cellin.2025.100254>
- Justice J, Miller JD, Newman JC, et al (2016) Frameworks for Proof-of-Concept Clinical Trials of Interventions That Target Fundamental Aging Processes. *J Gerontol A Biol Sci Med Sci* 71:1415–1423. <https://doi.org/10.1093/gerona/glw126>
- Kanherkar RR, Bhatia-Dey N, Makarev E, Csoka AB (2014) Cellular reprogramming for understanding and treating human disease. *Front Cell Dev Biol* 2:. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fcell.2014.00067>
- Kauffman S (1993) *The Origins of Order*. Oxford University Press.
- Kaur A, Macip S, Stover CM (2020) An Appraisal on the Value of Using Nutraceutical Based Senolytics and Senostatics in Aging. *Front Cell Dev Biol* 8:218. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fcell.2020.00218>
- Kennedy BK, Berger SL, Brunet A, et al (2014) Geroscience: Linking Aging to Chronic Disease. *Cell* 159:709–713. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cell.2014.10.039>
- Kerdemelidis S, Fiorenza NC (2023) Leveraging Pharmacoeconomics and Advance Market Commitments to Reduce Healthcare Expenditures. In: *Fed. Am. Sci.* <https://fas.org/publication/leveraging-pharmacoeconomics-and-advance-market-commitments-to-reduce-healthcare-expenditures/>. Accessed 10 Dec 2025
- Khaltourina D, Matveyev Y, Alekseev A, et al (2020) Aging Fits the Disease Criteria of the International Classification of Diseases. *Mech Ageing Dev* 189:111230. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.mad.2020.111230>
- Kim E-C, Kim J-R (2019) Senotherapeutics: Emerging strategy for healthy aging and age-related disease. *BMB Rep* 52:47–55
- Kirkland JL, Tchkonina T (2020) Senolytic drugs: from discovery to translation. *J Intern Med* 288:518–536. <https://doi.org/10.1111/joim.13141>

- Kirkwood TBL (1977) Evolution of ageing. *Nature* 270:301–304.
<https://doi.org/10.1038/270301a0>
- Koltko-Rivera ME (2006) Rediscovering the Later Version of Maslow’s Hierarchy of Needs: Self-Transcendence and Opportunities for Theory, Research, and Unification. *Rev Gen Psychol* 10:302–317. <https://doi.org/10.1037/1089-2680.10.4.302>
- Kritchevsky S, Zamora E, Bhasin S, et al (2025) Selecting Appropriate Clinical Trial Endpoints for Geroscience Trials: A Path Towards Consensus
- Kuan V, Fraser HC, Hingorani M, et al (2021) Data-driven identification of ageing-related diseases from electronic health records. *Sci Rep* 11:2938. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41598-021-82459-y>
- Kuhn TS (1962) *The Structure of Scientific Revolutions*, 1st edn. University of Chicago Press
- Li S, Agudelo Garcia PA, Aliferis C, et al (2025) Advancing biological understanding of cellular senescence with computational multiomics. *Nat Genet* 57:2381–2394.
<https://doi.org/10.1038/s41588-025-02314-y>
- López-Otín C, Blasco MA, Partridge L, et al (2013) The Hallmarks of Aging. *Cell* 153:1194–1217. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cell.2013.05.039>
- López-Otín C, Blasco MA, Partridge L, et al (2023) Hallmarks of aging: An expanding universe. *Cell* 186:243–278. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cell.2022.11.001>
- Lorenzo EC, Torrance BL, Haynes L (2023) Impact of senolytic treatment on immunity, aging, and disease. *Front Aging* 4:1161799. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fragi.2023.1161799>
- Lu Y, Brommer B, Tian X, et al (2020) Reprogramming to recover youthful epigenetic information and restore vision. *Nature* 588:124–129. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41586-020-2975-4>
- Lucke JC, Herbert D, Partridge B, Hall WD (2010) Anticipating the use of life extension technologies: Possible pointers from the adoption of assisted reproductive technologies. *EMBO Rep* 11:334–338. <https://doi.org/10.1038/embor.2010.48>
- Lucy JA (1997) Linguistic Relativity. *Annu Rev Anthropol* 26:291–312.
<https://doi.org/10.1146/annurev.anthro.26.1.291>
- Makarev E, Schubert AD, Kanherkar RR, et al (2017) In silico analysis of pathways activation landscape in oral squamous cell carcinoma and oral leukoplakia. *Cell Death Discov* 3:17022. <https://doi.org/10.1038/cddiscovery.2017.22>
- Marín Penella G (2024) Should the European Medicines Agency consider ageing a disease? *Bioethics* 38:431–437. <https://doi.org/10.1111/bioe.13265>

- Martela F, Ryan RM (2023) Clarifying Eudaimonia and Psychological Functioning to Complement Evaluative and Experiential Well-Being: Why Basic Psychological Needs Should Be Measured in National Accounts of Well-Being. *Perspect Psychol Sci* 18:1121–1135. <https://doi.org/10.1177/17456916221141099>
- Marzetti E, Calvani R, Picca A (2025) From promise to practice: Overcoming the barriers to unlock gerotherapeutics. *J Nutr Health Aging* 29:100639. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jnha.2025.100639>
- Maslow AH (1954) *Motivation and Personality*. Harper & Row
- Masny M (2023) Healthspan extension, completeness of life and justice. *Bioethics* 37:239–245. <https://doi.org/10.1111/bioe.13129>
- Maus M, López-Polo V, Mateo L, et al (2023) Iron accumulation drives fibrosis, senescence and the senescence-associated secretory phenotype. *Nat Metab* 5:2111–2130. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s42255-023-00928-2>
- Mayr E (1974) Teleological and Teleonomic, a New Analysis. In: Cohen RS, Wartofsky MW (eds) *A Portrait of Twenty-five Years*. Springer Netherlands, Dordrecht, pp 133–159
- Mendoza-Núñez VM, Mendoza-Soto AB (2024) Is Aging a Disease? A Critical Review Within the Framework of Ageism. *Cureus*. <https://doi.org/10.7759/cureus.54834>
- Muscedere J, Shorey CL, Duque G, et al (2025) Advancing Geroscience Research – A Scoping Review of Regulatory Environments for Gerotherapeutics. *J Nutr Health Aging* 29:100637. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jnha.2025.100637>
- Nernekli K, Mangarova DB, Suryadevara V, et al (2025) MRI detection of senescent cells in porcine knee joints with a β -galactosidase responsive Gd-chelate. *Npj Imaging* 3:18. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s44303-025-00078-y>
- Ng SK, Tawiah R, Sawyer M, Scuffham P (2018) Patterns of multimorbid health conditions: a systematic review of analytical methods and comparison analysis. *Int J Epidemiol* 47:1687–1704. <https://doi.org/10.1093/ije/dyy134>
- Nguyen TQT, Cho KA (2025) Targeting immunosenescence and inflammaging: advancing longevity research. *Exp Mol Med* 57:1881–1892. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s12276-025-01527-9>
- Niccoli T, Partridge L (2012) Ageing as a risk factor for disease. *Curr Biol* 22:R741–R752. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cub.2012.07.024>
- Olshansky SJ, Perry D, Miller RA, Butler RN (2007) Pursuing the Longevity Dividend: Scientific Goals for an Aging World. *Ann N Y Acad Sci* 1114:11–13. <https://doi.org/10.1196/annals.1396.050>

- Ovadya Y, Landsberger T, Leins H, et al (2018) Impaired immune surveillance accelerates accumulation of senescent cells and aging. *Nat Commun* 9:5435. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41467-018-07825-3>
- Oxford English Dictionary Meta-, prefix
- Pellegrino E (2005) The “Telos” of Medicine and the Good of the Patient. In: Thomasma DC, Weisstub DN, Kushner TK, Viafora C (eds) *Clinical Bioethics*. Springer-Verlag, Berlin/Heidelberg, pp 21–32
- Peng Y, Ding L, Song M, et al (2023) Acting on ethics and governance of aging research. *Trends Mol Med* 29:419–421. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.molmed.2023.03.004>
- Powell J, Chen S (2017) The problem of biology and anti-aging: A critical commentary. *Trends Med* 17:. <https://doi.org/10.15761/TiM.1000102>
- Prados-Torres A, Calderón-Larrañaga A, Hanco-Saavedra J, et al (2014) Multimorbidity patterns: a systematic review. *J Clin Epidemiol* 67:254–266. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jclinepi.2013.09.021>
- Prasanna PG, Citrin DE, Hildesheim J, et al (2021) Therapy-Induced Senescence: Opportunities to Improve Anticancer Therapy. *JNCI J Natl Cancer Inst* 113:1285–1298. <https://doi.org/10.1093/jnci/djab064>
- Pusparum M, Thas O, Beck S, et al (2025) From ageing clocks to human digital twins in personalising healthcare through biological age analysis. *Npj Digit Med* 8:537. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41746-025-01911-9>
- Qooja S, Roberts MJ, Fakher N, et al (2025) Is T-cell senescence associated with inflammatory arthritis and disease burden? A systematic review. *Semin Arthritis Rheum* 73:152757. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.semarthrit.2025.152757>
- Rattan S (2014) Aging is not a disease: implications for intervention. *Aging Dis*. <https://doi.org/10.14336/ad.2014.0500196>
- Reznek L (1987) *The Nature of Disease*. Routledge
- Rindler W (1956) Visual Horizons in World Models. *Mon Not R Astron Soc* 116:662–677. <https://doi.org/10.1093/mnras/116.6.662>
- Robbins PD, Jurk D, Khosla S, et al (2021) Senolytic Drugs: Reducing Senescent Cell Viability to Extend Health Span. *Annu Rev Pharmacol Toxicol* 61:779–803. <https://doi.org/10.1146/annurev-pharmtox-050120-105018>
- Rolland Y, Sierra F, Ferrucci L, et al (2023) Challenges in developing Geroscience trials. *Nat Commun* 14:5038. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41467-023-39786-7>
- Ross SM (1972) *Introduction to probability models*, 1st edn. Academic Press, New York

- Ryff CD (2014) Psychological Well-Being Revisited: Advances in the Science and Practice of Eudaimonia. *Psychother Psychosom* 83:10–28. <https://doi.org/10.1159/000353263>
- Ryle G (1949) *The Concept of Mind*. Routledge
- Saborido C, García-Barranquero P (2022) Is Aging a Disease? The Theoretical Definition of Aging in the Light of the Philosophy of Medicine. *J Med Philos Forum Bioeth Philos Med* 47:770–783. <https://doi.org/10.1093/jmp/jhac030>
- Sagitov S, Eriksson L, Cvijovic M (2024) A multitype Galton-Watson model for rejuvenating cells
- Saliev T, Singh PB (2025) Age reprogramming: Innovations and ethical considerations for prolonged longevity. *Biomed Rep* 22:1–12. <https://doi.org/10.3892/br.2025.1974>
- Salmon WC (1984) *Scientific Explanation and the Causal Structure of the World*. Princeton University Press
- Sarkar TJ, Quarta M, Mukherjee S, et al (2020) Transient non-integrative expression of nuclear reprogramming factors promotes multifaceted amelioration of aging in human cells. *Nat Commun* 11:1545. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41467-020-15174-3>
- Schellnegger M, Hofmann E, Carnieletto M, Kamolz L-P (2024) Unlocking longevity: the role of telomeres and its targeting interventions. *Front Aging* 5:1339317. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fragi.2024.1339317>
- Scholkopf B, Locatello F, Bauer S, et al (2021) Toward Causal Representation Learning. *Proc IEEE* 109:612–634. <https://doi.org/10.1109/JPROC.2021.3058954>
- Schrödinger E (1944) *What is Life?: The Physical Aspect of the Living Cell*. Cambridge: Cambridge University Press.
- Schulz S, Jansen L (2013) Formal Ontologies in Biomedical Knowledge Representation. *Yearb Med Inform* 22:132–146. <https://doi.org/10.1055/s-0038-1638845>
- Scott AJ, Ellison M, Sinclair DA (2021) The economic value of targeting aging. *Nat Aging* 1:616–623. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s43587-021-00080-0>
- Serra A, Mozgunov P, Jaki T (2022) An order restricted multi-arm multi-stage clinical trial design. *Stat Med* 41:1613–1626. <https://doi.org/10.1002/sim.9314>
- Smith B, Ceusters W (2010) Ontological realism: A methodology for coordinated evolution of scientific ontologies. *Appl Ontol* 5:139–188. <https://doi.org/10.3233/AO-2010-0079>
- Song P, An J, Zou M-H (2020) Immune Clearance of Senescent Cells to Combat Ageing and Chronic Diseases. *Cells* 9:671. <https://doi.org/10.3390/cells9030671>

- Stambler I (2017) Recognizing Degenerative Aging as a Treatable Medical Condition: Methodology and Policy. *Aging Dis* 8:583. <https://doi.org/10.14336/AD.2017.0130>
- Stambler I, Alekseev A, Matveyev Y, Khaltourina D (2022) Advanced pathological ageing should be represented in the ICD. *Lancet Healthy Longev* 3:e11. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S2666-7568\(21\)00305-6](https://doi.org/10.1016/S2666-7568(21)00305-6)
- Stoddard LD (1980) Toward a new human pathology: I. Biopathological populations, or sets: A substitute for the old pathology's diseases. *Hum Pathol* 11:228–239. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0046-8177\(80\)80004-9](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0046-8177(80)80004-9)
- Subramanian I, Verma S, Kumar S, et al (2020) Multi-omics Data Integration, Interpretation, and Its Application. *Bioinforma Biol Insights* 14:117793221989905. <https://doi.org/10.1177/1177932219899051>
- Suda M, Shimizu I, Katsuomi G, et al (2021) Senolytic vaccination improves normal and pathological age-related phenotypes and increases lifespan in progeroid mice. *Nat Aging* 1:1117–1126. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s43587-021-00151-2>
- Suryadevara V, Baratto L, Von Kruechten R, et al (2024) [18F]FPyGal PET TRACER DETECTS SENESENCE IN HUMAN OSTEOARTHRITIC SPECIMENS. *Osteoarthr Imaging* 4:100205. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ostima.2024.100205>
- Tizazu AM, Tessema EA, Cexus ONf (2025) Targeting immunosenescence promotes clearance of senescent cells. *Immun Ageing* 22:35. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12979-025-00518-8>
- Tournas L, Marchant GE (2019) The Fountain of Youth Revisited: Regulatory Challenges and Pathways for Healthspan Promoting Interventions. *Food Drug Law J* 74:1–28
- Valderas JM, Starfield B, Sibbald B, et al (2009) Defining Comorbidity: Implications for Understanding Health and Health Services. *Ann Fam Med* 7:357–363. <https://doi.org/10.1370/afm.983>
- Welzel C, Ostermann M, Smith HL, et al (2025) Enabling secure and self determined health data sharing and consent management. *Npj Digit Med* 8:560. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41746-025-01945-z>
- West MD, Labat I, Sternberg H, et al (2018) Use of deep neural network ensembles to identify embryonic-fetal transition markers: repression of *COX7A1* in embryonic and cancer cells. *Oncotarget* 9:7796–7811. <https://doi.org/10.18632/oncotarget.23748>
- West MD, Pereira-Smith OM, Smith JR (1989) Replicative senescence of human skin fibroblasts correlates with a loss of regulation and overexpression of collagenase activity. *Exp Cell Res* 184:138–147. [https://doi.org/10.1016/0014-4827\(89\)90372-8](https://doi.org/10.1016/0014-4827(89)90372-8)
- West MD, Shay JW, Wright WE, Linskens MHK (1996) Altered expression of plasminogen activator and plasminogen activator inhibitor during cellular senescence. *Exp Gerontol* 31:175–193. [https://doi.org/10.1016/0531-5565\(95\)02013-6](https://doi.org/10.1016/0531-5565(95)02013-6)

- Whorf BL (1956) The relation of habitual thought and behavior to language. In J. B. Carroll (Ed.), *Language, Thought, and Reality: Selected Writings of Benjamin Lee Whorf*. MIT Press
- World Health Organization (2009) *Practical guidance for scaling up health service innovations*
- Xiang X, Dong C, Zhou L, et al (2024) Novel PET Imaging Probe for Quantitative Detection of Senescence In Vivo. *J Med Chem* 67:5924–5934. <https://doi.org/10.1021/acs.jmedchem.4c00179>
- Xie M, Fussenegger M (2018) Designing cell function: assembly of synthetic gene circuits for cell biology applications. *Nat Rev Mol Cell Biol* 19:507–525. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41580-018-0024-z>
- Xu M, Pirtskhalava T, Farr JN, et al (2018) Senolytics improve physical function and increase lifespan in old age. *Nat Med* 24:1246–1256. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41591-018-0092-9>
- Yoshida S, Nakagami H, Hayashi H, et al (2020) The CD153 vaccine is a senotherapeutic option for preventing the accumulation of senescent T cells in mice. *Nat Commun* 11:2482. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41467-020-16347-w>
- Yoshimori M (2025) Unlocking the longevity dividend for growth and resilience. In: *Fair Obs.*
- Zhang L, Pitcher LE, Yousefzadeh MJ, et al (2022) Cellular senescence: a key therapeutic target in aging and diseases. *J Clin Invest* 132:e158450. <https://doi.org/10.1172/JCI158450>
- Zhavoronkov A, Bhullar B (2015) Classifying aging as a disease in the context of ICD-11. *Front Genet* 6:. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fgene.2015.00326>
- Zhou Z, Liu Y, Feng Y, et al (2023) Engineering longevity—design of a synthetic gene oscillator to slow cellular aging. *Science* 380:376–381. <https://doi.org/10.1126/science.add7631>
- Zhu Y, Tchkonina T, Pirtskhalava T, et al (2015) The Achilles’ heel of senescent cells: from transcriptome to senolytic drugs. *Aging Cell* 14:644–658. <https://doi.org/10.1111/acel.12344>